

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 1: Visualization module

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Abstract

This tutorial discusses the Visualization module. It showcases the module's general capabilities and provides concrete examples of using it in practice.

Keywords: JECDM, visualization, plot, heatmap, parallel coordinate plot, convergence plot

Contents

1 Introduction	2	4 General plot for 3D visualization	22
2 Understanding fundamental concepts	2	4.1 Creating and displaying a plot [T]	23
2.1 The multilevel data processing	2	4.2 Creating and uploading data sets [T]	24
2.2 A brief discussion on the queuing system	2	4.3 Creating a colorbar and using a non-coordinate-dependent gradient [T]	26
2.3 Understanding display ranges (manager)	3	4.4 Using nonlinear scales [T]	26
2.4 Understanding data sets	5	4.5 Examining marker style configurations [T]	27
2.5 General overview of the hierarchy of the highest-level GUI components	6	5 Convergence plot for 2D visualization [T]	27
3 General plot for 2D visualization	7	5.1 Creating and displaying a convergence plot	28
3.1 Creating and displaying a plot [T]	7	5.2 Using nonlinear scales [T]	29
3.2 Basics on creating and uploading a data set (fixed display ranges) [T]	8	6 Parallel coordinate plot for 2D visualization	29
3.3 Using dynamic display ranges [T]	10	6.1 Creating and displaying a parallel coordinate plot [T]	30
3.4 Drawing continuous lines [T]	10	6.2 Providing multiple data sets [T]	31
3.5 Introducing breaks into rendered lines [T]	10	6.3 Customizing the plot [T]	31
3.6 Establishing a custom display ranges mapping [T]	11	6.4 Using custom display ranges [T]	32
3.7 Using multiple data sets and enabling the legend [T]	12	7 Heatmap for 2D visualization	33
3.8 Customizing the legend [T]	13	7.1 Creating and displaying a plot [T]	33
3.9 Using gradients [T]	14	7.2 Customizing the plot [T]	35
3.10 Gradient customization [T]	15	7.3 Using nonlinear scales and displaying regular data sets [T]	35
3.11 Creating a colorbar and using a non-coordinate-dependent gradient [T]	17	7.4 Using a heatmap to illustrate a density function [T]	36
3.12 Turning off drawing area clipping [T]	19	7.5 Data presorting and interval-based filtering [T]	37
3.13 Examining marker style configurations [T]	19	7.6 Mask-based filtering [T]	40
3.14 Using nonlinear scales [T]	19	8 Heatmap for 3D visualization	41
		8.1 Creating and displaying a plot [T]	41
		8.2 Customizing the plot [T]	41
		8.3 Using nonlinear scales [T]	41
		8.4 Using a heatmap to illustrate a density function [T]	41
		8.5 Data presorting and interval-based filtering [T]	42

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8.6	Mask-based filtering [T]	43
8.7	Bucket style customization [T]	43
9	Customizing the top-level Swing-based components	44
9.1	Creating a custom plot wrapper [T]	44
9.2	Creating a custom plots wrapper [T]	48
10	On the data updater	49
10.1	Creating data updating system – an example [T]	52

1. Introduction

Visualization plays an essential role when working with multi-dimensional data. This is the case for this framework’s two major research streams: multi-objective optimization and multi-criteria decision aiding. Visualization can help not only understand the final outcomes but may also be a valuable tool during the development, as it may provide better insight into various ongoing processes. Hence, creating a separate visualization module was only a natural decision when designing JECDM.

This module was made almost from scratch, with external libraries’ assistance reduced to a minimum. The motivation for such extensive additional work was twofold:

- This module is intended to be an inherent part of JECDM, independent to a large degree from external sources. This way, high-level integration with other modules could be ensured (e.g., by keeping API consistent throughout the framework).
- There is no single procedure for visualization that would be highly efficient in all possible contexts (the “no free lunch” theorem). For instance, an implemented visualization tool may perform vastly differently depending on whether the data to be illustrated is assumed to be constant or changing. Developing this module from scratch allowed me to take control and suitably develop it to fit the general framework’s needs best.

Regarding the technology used, the module is founded on Java Swing (windows, panels, etc.). This ensures integrity with the Java language and platform independence. Knowledge of Java Swing is thus also a prerequisite for using this module (the tutorials will not cover Java Swing). As for rendering options, the two modes available:

- *Rendering in 2D*: In the current library version, 2D rendering is performed entirely via Java Swing, which also means it is performed on the CPU (which may be a bottleneck for large data sets to be illustrated). GPU-based 2D rendering is in plans for future development.
- *Rendering in 3D*: 3D rendering is implemented using OpenGL technology. Thus, the rendering is done on the GPU, releasing the CPU. This graphics mode was developed with the assistance of the free-to-use JOGL library (<https://jogamp.org/jogl/www/>). Nonetheless, the rendering results are still finally displayed using the Swing components.

2. Understanding fundamental concepts

This section briefly discusses selected concepts that are elemental to the visualization module. Acquainting yourself with them is a prerequisite for using the offered tools unhinderedly.

2.1. The multilevel data processing

Let me guide you through the sequential process of how the framework processes the input data for visualization. This process is methodically decomposed into four distinct steps:

1. **Determining the bounds for the input attribute values.** These bounds are called “display ranges” in the framework’s source codes. These bounds can be fixed (provided by the user) or determined dynamically during data upload.
2. **Normalizing the input data.** The bounds determined in (1) are used to normalize the input data, which can be considered data standardization.
3. **Determining the coordinates in the rendering space.** This step projects the normalized points into the rendering space. For example, the rendering space can be the bounds of the JPanel used for rendering in 2D visualization mode.
4. **Executing extra processing.** This step is reserved for some additional, context-specific processing. In the current library version, it is used in the 3D mode to construct data buffers to be uploaded to GPU.

Important notes: the outputs from all the above steps are kept in the memory (until the visualization context changes, e.g., input data or window size); the final output is a render (*java.awt.image.BufferedImage*).

The rationale for such a decomposition was twofold. First, it helped establish a modular code structure with low redundancy, high-level abstractions, and the power to be easily extended. Second, such a structurization allowed for ensuring processing efficiency. For example, imagine that the user has resized the window. Clearly, the window-resized event does not affect the validity of the data generated in steps (1) and (2) (the data in these steps is independent of the window size). Thus, only step (3) has to be executed to generate a new render. As another example, consider 3D visualization and assume that the user changes the projection (translates or rotates the camera). In the current implementations, it does not affect any of these steps (1-4). Their outputs remain valid. Only the generation of a new render is called (with the projection matrix suitably revised).

Extra: For those interested in making their own core-level implementations, I recommend starting with looking at *dataset.painter.IPainter* and *dataset.painter.AbstractPainter*. The ‘painters’ are associated with input data sets to be displayed, and they execute the above-discussed processing.

2.2. A brief discussion on the queuing system

Before moving to the “coding part,” let me first explain the means implemented for the visualization tool to ensure satisfactory processing efficiency (which can be un-

derstood not only strictly from the computational perspective but also from the user's perspective, i.e., responsiveness, non-freezing GUI, etc.). A simple yet very effective queueing system was implemented to satisfy these needs (see the conceptual scheme in Figure 1). The Queueing System (QS; *swing.swingworkerqueue.QueueingSystem*) comprises a desired number of Swing Worker Queues (SWQ; *swing.swingworkerqueue.SwingWorkerQueue*), and each queue is associated with a different set of plots in the system (all queues will cover all plots, the assignment is done dynamically and is as equal as possible). E.g., in Figure 1, the first queue is associated with plots 1 and 2, while the second queue is linked to plots 3 and 4.

Figure 1: The queueing system

Whenever something relevant for visualization happens in the system, e.g., new data is uploaded, the processing tasks to be executed are formulated and registered in the appropriate queue as the Execution Block (EB; *swing.swingworkerqueue.ExecutionBlock*). Each block thus represents some specific job that needs to be done and is assigned a relevant plot ID and predefined task ID. Further, each block consists of more particular sub-tasks: Queued Swing Workers (QSW; *swing.swingworkerqueue.QueuedSwingWorkers*). As the name suggests, the QSW extends *javax.swing.SwingWorker<T,V>*. Thus, they are executed on a dedicated swing thread pool. Note that the number of queues can be provided as a parameter (see *plotswrapper.AbstractPlotsWrapper.Params.noUpdatersQueues*; the *AbstractPlotsWrapper* class will be discussed later).

The queueing system obeys the following rules:

- The SWQ implements the first-in-first-out queue.
- Only one EB can be processed at a time in a single queue.
- When an EB finishes processing, the next EB in the queue is run (if it exists).
- The addition/removal/execution of EBs is synchronized using Java locks.

The above implies that up to n additional threads are running as background tasks, where n denotes the number of queues in the queueing system (thus, the parallelization is supported).

The goal of most of the designed EBs is to create the final render to be displayed. After completion, the reference to the render, maintained by the relevant JPanels, is updated (thus, something new can be displayed). However, what can be expected is that the execution of some of the EBs may take a very long time. Consequently, the queue may grow really fast, which will cause considerable delays in the results that the user can observe. To ease this problem, the concept of overdue was implemented. Specifically, each time an EB is added to the queue, it stores the registration timestamp. When it is its turn to be executed, the current time is compared with the registration timestamp. If (a) the delay is significant (can be specified by the user) and (b) it is not the last EB of its type (task and plot) in the queue, it is removed from the queue, and the system tries executing the next EB (the process is repeated until some EB is executed). This way, the visualization system can be interactive as it can skip the execution of overdue (timestamp comparison) and not up-to-date (not the newest of its type EB) tasks.

2.3. Understanding display ranges (manager)

Display Range. A Display Range (*drmanager.DisplayRangesManager.DisplayRange*) represents, in short, an interval associated with some specified input attribute dimension. It tells the visualization tool, what part of the original input space should be displayed (hence, display range). As already explained in Section 2.1, display ranges are essential in the first step of data processing in the implemented visualization system.

Consider Listing 2.3. It is a snippet from the *DisplayRange* class (an inner class of *drmanager.DisplayRangesManager*), focused on its main fields.

Listing 1: *DisplayRange* class, nested class of *drmanager.DisplayRangesManager* class.

```

/**
 * Container-like class representing a
 * display range linked to some
 * dimension/attribute/objective/etc.
 */
public static class DisplayRange
{
    /**
     * Display range (main field). Can be
     * null. If null, the data points are
     * not projected but are displayed as
     * they
     * are (normalization is ignored), given
     * the associated dimension.
     */
    private Range _R;

    /**
     * If true, display range is dynamically
     * updated when a new data set is
     * examined (given the linked dimension)
     */
    private final boolean _updateDynamically;

```

```

20  /**
    * If false and the {@link DisplayRange#
      _updateDynamically} flag is true, the
      display range is updated also
    * considering the past data. If true,
      the display range is recalculated
      from scratch.
    */
    private final boolean _updateFromScratch;

25  /**
    * Auxiliary object for normalizing the
      rendering/objective space.
    * It is used for transforming input data
      points into normalized coordinates
      and
    * executing reversed transformation (e.g
      ., when determining axes tick labels)
    */
    private AbstractMinMaxNormalization
      _normalizer;

30  [...]
  }

```

The first field, *Range* *_R*, represents a double interval (*Range* class, both sides are closed). As the comment says, *_R* can be null. If so, the normalization part is ignored (the input data is processed as it is). Notably, it is the main field of the *DisplayRange* class. **Note the prefix ‘_’**. It is used in this framework to denote fields (class variables). It is a notational convention. Now, imagine that an object instance is associated with an X-axis, and you want to limit its displayed part to *[-5, 5]*. To do so, you have to set *_R* to *[-5, 5]* (i.e., *_R = new Range(-5.0d, 5.0d)*; the constructors are often self-explanatory in the framework).

Consider the following field, *boolean* *_updateDynamically*. Any time a new data set is specified for visualization, the higher-level class that wraps all the display ranges (*drmanager.DisplayRangesManager*; will be covered later) is called to update the bounds (see *drmanager.DisplayRangesManager#updateDisplayRanges(Data data)*). Any display range object whose *_updateDynamically* flag is set to true will be re-examined, i.e., its *_R* field will be updated based on the input data (and associated attribute). This way, the user may tell that (s)he wants the visualization tool to determine display ranges. The procedure involved will set them so that they are spanned over minimal and maximal values in the data set.

Next, *boolean* *_updateFromScratch* represents the updating policy and matters only if *_updateDynamically = true*. If *_updateFromScratch = true*, the display range will be recalculated, ignoring past data updates (so only currently supplied data will matter). If *_updateFromScratch = false*, any time the display range is updated, the newly determined bounds are compared against the currently stored ones. The final bounds will comprise ‘smaller minima’ and ‘greater maxima.’ This way, the bounds will tend to expand throughout the series of

data updates (shrinking will not be possible).

Finally, the *AbstractMinMaxNormalization* *_normalizer* object tells how the linked dimension can be projected into normalized space, given the bounds specified in *_R*. This object should extend *space.normalization.AbstractMinMaxNormalization*, whose primary method is *getNormalized(double value)* that returns a normalized input. In this class’s extensions, the normalization is performed based on expected minimal and maximal values. The representative of such normalization procedures is a standard min-max normalization: *normalized = (input - min)/(max - min)* that linearly interpolates the input into some value from *[0, 1]* interval. It is implemented as *space.normalization.Linear* class (in the *Utils* module) and the *_normalizer* field will be fed with this class instance by default. Note that using a different normalizer will allow you to manipulate the scales in the rendered plot (e.g., use a logarithmic scale).

Display Ranges manager. All display ranges are maintained by a *DisplayRangesManager* class. First and foremost, it stores the relevant objects and provides various functions for updating the internal data. You can suitably parameterize the object instance and adjust the expected visualization result.

Consider the snippet of this class presented in Listing 2. Its main field is the array of all display ranges involved (i.e., *DisplayRange[]* *_DR*). Different plots will make different implicit assumptions regarding which object means what. For instance, the standard *Plot2D* class (*plot.plot2D*) assumes that the first display range is associated with the X-axis, while the second with Y. However, even for the simple 2D plot, **you may be willing to specify more display ranges** (this will be explained later). In short, if you use *Plot2D*, *_DR[0]* represents the bounds for the X-axis, while *_DR[1]* for Y.

Listing 2: *DisplayRangesManager* class

```

/**
 * Display ranges manager is responsible
   for maintaining all data linked to
   display bounds imposed for rendering
 * (min/max values per each dimension to be
   portrayed). Used for properly
   projecting (normalizing) data points
 * to be displayed.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class DisplayRangesManager
{
  [...]

  /**
   * Stores data on display ranges.
   */
  protected DisplayRange [] _DR;

  /**
   * Additional field for mapping the data
     point index to display range index (

```

```

        usually 1:1 mapping). Can be null if
        the attribute does not affect a
        display range.
    */
    protected Integer[] _attIdx_to_drIdx;
    [...]
}

```

The following attribute, i.e., `Integer [] _attIdx_to_drIdx`, tells how different attributes map into display ranges. The structure of the input data will be discussed in Section 2.4, but as for now, assume that a single data point is a double vector whose elements can be called attributes, i.e., `double [] v = {attribute_1, attribute_2, attribute_m}`. The `_attIdx_to_drIdx` field helps customize the linkage between the attributes and the rendering space dimensions. By default, the connection is `_attIdx_to_drIdx[i] = i`, meaning the *i*-th attribute should map into the *i*-th dimension. But imagine that you want to swap the axes in Plot 2D. You can reverse the mapping to achieve this, i.e., `_attIdx_to_drIdx[0] = 1` and `_attIdx_to_drIdx[1] = 0`. Additionally, as the comment states, you can set `_attIdx_to_drIdx[i] = null` if the *i*-th attribute has no meaning for visualization. It effectively ‘disables’ some attributes, which can be handy if you already have more-than-needed-dimensional data loaded in the memory and do not want to waste time on data conversion.

2.4. Understanding data sets

Now, let me provide an overview of the data set class `dataset.DataSet`, whose instances are the primary inputs for visualization. In some sense, one data set consists of semantically consistent raw data (e.g., one data set can represent results attained by one algorithm in experimental verification). Its main fields are given in code snippet 3 (note that these fields are inherited from the abstract `dataset.AbstractDataSet` class).

Listing 3: `AbstractDataSet` class

```

/**
 * Abstract class representation of a data
 * set.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public abstract class AbstractDataSet
    implements IDataset
{
    /**
     * Data set name.
     */
    protected String _name = "";

    /**
     * Current data to be displayed.
     */
    protected final Data _data;

    [...]

    /**

```

```

 * Data set painter.
 */
protected IPainter _painter;

/**
 * If true, the data set is displayable
 * on legend, false otherwise.
 */
protected volatile boolean
    _displayableOnLegend = true;

/**
 * If true, the data set rendering is
 * skipped
 */
protected volatile boolean _skipRendering
    = false;

/**
 * Auxiliary mask that tell whether the
 * update of the i-th display range
 * should be skipped.
 * Can return null (not used). Obviously,
 * the mask has no effect when updating
 * display ranges is globally disabled.
 */
protected boolean[]
    _skipDisplayRangeUpdateMask;

[...]
}

```

Naturally, a data set can be named (`String _name` field). The stored value will be used when employing a legend for visualization (data set entry label). Next, the actual input (raw) data is stored in `Data _data` (see code snippet 4). As can be observed, this field is final. Furthermore, the `dataset.Data` class is immutable (almost, the constructor accepts the raw data but does not copy it; one could keep the reference to data and alter it, but there is no reason to do so; the copying was not implemented for efficiency reasons). In the current library version, one cannot change – except in an above-given way – the internal data of the already uploaded data set object. What one can do is set new data set objects to be visualized. The reason was to ensure the high-level safety of data processing by prohibiting some partial data alternations. The only alternation path is to provide a new (almost) immutable input at the highest API level.

Listing 4: `Data` class

```

/**
 * Container-like class representing data
 * for rendering.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class Data
{
    /**
     * Raw data. A linked list is used as the
     * data may be collected by receiving
     * various batches, but all stored

```

```

10  * arrays are interpreted as contiguous.
    Each element of the double array is a
    point to be visualized.
    * Note that the elements of the linked
    list can be null. If so, the lines
    are broken at these points (this is
    * the interpretation of the default
    painter). Nulls in stored arrays have
    no meaning (are skipped).
    */
    private final LinkedList<double [][]>
15     _data;
    [...]
    }

```

Let us look now into the *dataset.Data* class (see snippet 4). The main field is the raw data, and it is of the following type: *private final LinkedList<double[][]> _data*. First, at the bottom, the data is a double matrix (*double [][]*). The visualization system assumes that each matrix row (the first dimension) is one input data point (point to be displayed). This data point is a double vector, of course. Each element of this vector is the earlier-discussed attribute that can be (or not) mapped onto a display range. The matrix entries (vectors) that are nulled are, by default, ignored by the system.

At the top, the double matrix is just an element of a list that can be passed via the constructor. The reason for accepting a list was to give a possibility to incrementally update data on the data-generator part (e.g., optimizer) without needing to copy & paste the data exhaustively. Important note: The list elements can be null. These nulls are, by default, considered breaking points for lines (when the data set is to be illustrated as lines).

Let me move back to (*Abstract*)*DataSet* class. The following field is an object implementing an *dataset.painter.IPainter* interface. Each data set is assigned one painter. The painter’s job is to execute the processing discussed in Section 2.1 and to generate a final render. As may be expected, the painters perform lower-level processes. To ensure a higher safety level, the user cannot explicitly provide the painter object in the current API. The *DataSet* constructor has protected access, and the only way to obtain its instance is to call one of the static methods available in *DataSet* that have self-explanatory names, e.g., “*public static DataSet getFor2D(String name, MarkerStyle ms, LineStyle ls)*.” These methods establish a proper painter instance. Note that the marker and line styles are major painter’s fields, but they will be covered later.

The following two fields of (*Abstract*)*DataSet* that are worth covering are *boolean _displayableOnLegend* and *boolean _skipRendering*. The names are self-explanatory. These flags were introduced to allow the user to creatively customize (or bypass the framework’s limitations) what has to be rendered. For instance, the legend layout is determined based on the maintained data sets, i.e., one cannot customize it manually. Suppose one needs to add some additional entries that may have come with context-specific interpretations but do not want to add additional data to be displayed. In that case, he or she can create a dummy data set object with specified marker and line styles

but having no data specified and has *boolean _skipRendering* flag set to true. As another example, imagine that it is more convenient for the user to model a data set as two instances of *DataSet*, but still (s)he wants to use just one legend entry. If so, the *boolean _displayableOnLegend* flag of one of these data sets can be set to false.

The last presented field is “*boolean [] _skipDisplayRangeUpdateMask*”. It allows individually, i.e., per data set – disabling the update of specific display range ranges when a plot is supplied with new data sets. This field may prove useful when creating creatively customized visualization.

2.5. General overview of the hierarchy of the highest-level GUI components

This section provides a general overview of the hierarchy of the highest-level GUI components (such as *plot.Plot*). Note that these components will be discussed more extensively later. They are brought here just to provide you with an understanding of the framework’s capabilities. The list below provides these from the lowest to the highest-level class. They are, however, expressed as packages in the list as one component is often a product of several classes (abstract class, model/view/counterparts, etc.).

1. **Plot (see *plot* package):** The plot component (extensions of *AbstractPanel* that extends *JPanel*) represents, as the name suggests, a plot (e.g., *plot.Plot2D* or *plot.Plot3D*). It can be considered the lowest-level component from the GUI development perspective (naturally, there are lower-level per-plot components, e.g., legend, axis, etc.). This component is primarily responsible for creating and displaying renders, but other logic-related aspects are also covered, e.g., executing interactions with the plot.
2. **PlotWrapper (see *plotwrapper* package):** A single plot is wrapped by an extension of *plotwrapper.AbstractPlotWrapper* that directly extends a *JPanel*. This wrapper was introduced to allow the developer to construct a panel that consists of a plot and directly connected GUI components (buttons, sliders, etc.).
3. **PlotsWrapper (see *plotswrapper* package):** The plots (wrapped) existing in the system are then wrapped by some extension of *plotswrapper.AbstractPlotsWrapper* (also extends a *JPanel*). This panel was introduced to allow the construction of a panel consisting of several plots (with potentially associated GUI) and higher-level GUI. Apart from this simple purpose, the *plotswrapper.AbstractPlotsWrapper*, along with its model and controller counterparts, can be considered the core for processing. For instance, *plotswrapper.PlotsWrapperController* maintains the queueing system discussed in Section 2.2 (keeps the object, registers new jobs, etc.).
4. **Frame (see *frame* package):** At the top, the instance of a plots wrapper is handled by *frame.Frame* (extension of *JFrame*). This component primarily provides window-related functionalities (creating and displaying the window, managing window events, etc.).

3. General plot for 2D visualization

This section provides chronologically ordered (sub)tutorials focused on a general plot 2D (*plot.Plot2D*). The term “general” refers to the fact that this class is flexible and is a starting point for more specialized classes that extend it (e.g., *plot.parallelcoordinate.ParallelCoordinatePlot2D*). All the source codes linked to these tutorials can be found in the *t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d* package of the Visualization module. Note that they are not copied and pasted here entirely to avoid redundancy. Detailed comments already accompany the codes. Instead, the discussion will focus mainly on essentials, and only the most critical code snippets will be brought here. Also, as explained in Tutorial 0 (Overview), the locations of the codes being currently discussed will be provided in rectangular text boxes with gray backgrounds.

3.1. Creating and displaying a plot [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t1

This short (few lines of code; see Listing 5) tutorial explains how to create an empty 2D plot and how to display it. It also shows some basic customization options (e.g., turning off the axes). The expected window displayed when executing the program (executing the “main” method) is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The expected window containing the empty plot

There are several things worth noting in this tutorial. First, the window/panel-like components are extensions of swing components. Therefore, the API is, to a large extent, shared. Second, the parameterization methods used in this tutorial are commonly used throughout JECDM. Specifically, a class

that can be extensively parameterized will often have an inner “Params” class that serves as a container for various fields passed via the params object to the main class upon object instance creation (via the constructor). The fields are often accompanied by JavaDoc comments, clearly indicating their purpose. Naturally, there will usually be many shortcuts available. For instance, parameterized params constructors may be provided, a primary class constructor that creates the params container itself may also exist (to avoid explicit params creation), default params field values may be provided, or static factory methods that will have self-explanatory names and that will allow quickly creating context-specific parameterization will be supplied. Overall, as highlighted in Tutorial 0 (Overview), not everything will be covered in the tutorials, and it will be up to the programmer to inspect, e.g., the parameterization means.

Listing 5: Creating and displaying Plot2D

```
//Create the params container for 2D plot.
Plot2D.Params pP = new Plot2D.Params();

// Create a default display ranges manager
// (params container) for plot 2D.
// The known ranges are set to null but
// updated dynamically each time a new
// dataset is uploaded.
pP._pDisplayRangesManager =
    DisplayRangesManager.Params.getFor2D();

// This field specifies a title to be
// displayed above the plot.
// If nulled, the title is not displayed.
pP._title = "Tutorial 1";
//pP._title = null;

// Can be used to provide a title for the X
// -axis.
// If nulled, the title is not displayed (
// but does not affect ticks).
pP._xAxisTitle = "X-axis";
//pP._xAxisTitle = null;

// The flag below can be false (true, by
// default) to turn off displaying the X-
// axis (title and ticks).
//pP._drawXAxis = false;

// The basic parameterization for Y-axis is
// analogous:
pP._yAxisTitle = "Y-axis";
//pP._yAxisTitle = null;
//pP._drawYAxis = false;

// If you turn off the axes, you will be
// able to notice that the plot drawing
// area is not centered. The broader
// left margin is to provide more space for
// horizontally oriented tick labels of
// the Y-Axis. However,
// the visualization tool provides various
// customization means. A scheme object is
// one of the most fundamental
```

```

// customization components (see {scheme.
  AbstractScheme}). It is simply a
  container for key-value relationships
30 // that refer to various plot properties.
  The plot components implemented in JECDM
  are provided with a scheme
// object upon the creation so that they
  can be customized. The code below can be
  used to customize the plot
// margins. The "relative" term refers to
  the fact that margins can be
  dynamically determined based on the
// percent value of plot size (min of width
  and height). Note that if the scheme
  object is not provided
// via the constructor, it will be
  instantiated as scheme.WhiteScheme.
35
/*pP._scheme = new WhiteScheme();
pP._scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
  MARGIN_LEFT_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER,
  0.1f);
pP._scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
  MARGIN_RIGHT_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER,
  0.1f);
pP._scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
  MARGIN_BOTTOM_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER,
  0.1f);
40 pP._scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
  MARGIN_TOP_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER, 0.1
  f);*/

// Create the plot object:
Plot2D plot = new Plot2D(pP);

45 // Create the params object for the frame.
  The Params class provides various static
  methods that can be
// considered shortcuts. The below method
  creates a frame params object that is
  supposed to handle a
// single plot (the first argument), and
  the frame size (width and height) should
  be set to 50% of the
// minimum of the screen width and height (
  the second argument).
Frame.Params pF = Frame.Params.getParams(
  plot, 0.5f);
50

// One can specify the window title by
  using the below field.
pF._title = "Window title";

// The below line create a frame object.
55 Frame frame = new Frame(pF);

// The below piece of code can be used as a
  shortcut (no frame parameterization).
//Frame frame = new Frame(plot, 0.5f);
60

// Make the frame visible (Java Swing API)
frame.setVisible(true);

```

```

// You can also specify a new scheme (or
  adjust the maintained one) after the
  frame creation. It can be achieved
// by calling one of the "frame.
  updateScheme" methods. See the
  following code that changes the scheme
  to black.

65 /*AbstractScheme scheme = new BlackScheme()
  ;
pP._scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
  MARGIN_LEFT_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER,
  0.1f);
pP._scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
  MARGIN_RIGHT_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER,
  0.1f);
pP._scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
  MARGIN_BOTTOM_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER,
  0.1f);
70 pP._scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
  MARGIN_TOP_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER, 0.1
  f);
frame.updateScheme(scheme);*/

```

Second, the source code introduces the *AbstractScheme* class (*scheme* package), which can be suitably employed to customize the plot style. A scheme object contains multiple "size", "number", "color", "align", "font", and "flags" properties with adjustable values. Various plot components read them upon creation to adjust how they look. It is recommended that the user gets acquainted with this class (the properties' names are often self-explanatory and clearly indicate their purpose). As an example, Figure 3 illustrates the same plot as in Figure 2, but with the "*BlackScheme*" used (and with adjusted margins; can be achieved by uncommenting the last lines in Listing 5).

3.2. Basics on creating and uploading a data set (fixed display ranges) [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t2

This tutorial covers the basics on data set creation and upload. It first explains how to impose fixed (non-dynamic) display ranges for the X and Y axes (they are set to [1;2] and [0;1], respectively; see code snippet in Listing 6).

Listing 6: Fixed display ranges creation

```

Plot2D.Params pP = new Plot2D.Params();
// Create a default display ranges manager
  (params container) for plot 2D
pP._pDisplayRangesManager =
  DisplayRangesManager.Params.getFor2D();
// Fix both display ranges (for X and Y
  axis) and prohibit their dynamic update
  (overwrite the array elements)
5 // X-axis
pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[0] = new
  DisplayRangesManager.DisplayRange(new
  Range(1.0d, 2.0d), false);

```


Figure 3: The expected window containing the empty plot (black scheme with adjusted margins is used)

```
// Y-axis
pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[1] = new
    DisplayRangesManager.DisplayRange(Range.
        getNormalRange(), false);
```


Figure 4: A simple data set illustrated using a plot with fixed display ranges

As for another newly introduced step, this tutorial creates a data set object and executes plot data update (manually; there will be a dedicated “updater” class, but it will be covered in

the later parts of this document). The code snippet related to this part is provided in Listing 7. The reader is encouraged at this point to investigate other implemented marker styles (*dataset.painter.style.enums.Marker enum*). **Important note:** The data sets can only be provided once the frame is created.

The expected plot generated in this tutorial is depicted in Figure 2. Notably, one of the input data points is not displayed (i.e., [2.5, 1.5].) The reason is that it is outside of the imposed (fixed) display bounds.

Listing 7: Basic data set creation and plot update

```
// The data sets can be provided after the
// frame is created.
// Let's create the raw data first (each
// row is one data point). The first column
// is the X-attribute, while the
// second is Y.
double [][] data = new double [][]
5 {
    {1.0d, 0.0},
    {1.5d, 0.5d},
    {2.0d, 1.0d},
    {2.5d, 1.5d} // will not be visible
};
// The below line creates a marker style.
// This tutorial assumes that each data
// point is drawn using red dots
// (Marker.CIRCLE). The size of dots is set
// to 5% of the minimum of the plot width
// and height (in pixels; note
// that the size is implementation-
// dependent).
MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(5.0f,
    Color.RED, Marker.CIRCLE);
// The following two lines create the test
// data set and then upload it to the plot.
DataSet dataSet = DataSet.getFor2D("Test
    data set", data, ms);
plot.getModel().setDataSet(dataSet, true);
```

Note that the plot image for this document was generated explicitly from the program render. This functionality is implemented in *plot.AbstractPlot.getPlotScreenshot(boolean transparentBackground)* method. In this tutorial (and all the remaining ones), this method was called by using a save dialogue box accessible via the right-click button. See the code snippet from this tutorial in Listing 8.

Listing 8: Creating a popup menu with a “save as image” option.

```
// The API for JECMD 1.0 allows adding
// simple popup menus triggered when right-
// clicking on the plot. The
// following three lines create a popup
// menu, add a menu item that opens a save
// dialogue box (which allows
// saving the plot as an image), and
// register the popup menu.
RightClickPopupMenu menu = new
    RightClickPopupMenu();
menu.addItem(new SaveAsImage());
```

```
plot.getController().addRightClickPopupMenu
(menu);
```

3.3. Using dynamic display ranges [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t3

This brief tutorial differs from the case presented in Section 3.3 only by using dynamic display ranges instead of fixed ones. The expected plot is depicted in Figure 5. As can be noticed, the fourth data point is now illustrated as the X and Y axes automatically adjusted to cover its coordinates.

Figure 5: A simple data set illustrated using a plot with dynamic display ranges

3.4. Drawing continuous lines [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t4

This example introduces how to represent a data set as a continuous line. For this reason, the *LineStyle* class is introduced (see Listing 9). The expected outcome is presented in Figure 6.

Listing 9: Creating a continuous line

```
double [][] data = new double [][]
{
    {0.0d, 0.0},
    {0.25d, 0.25d},
    {0.5d, 0.5d},
    {0.75d, 0.25d},
    {1.0d, 1.0d},
};
```


Figure 6: A simple data set represented as a line

```
10 MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(5.0f,
    Color.RED, Marker.CIRCLE);

// The below line construct a line style
// object (line width set to 1% of minimum
// of plot width and height; color
// is set to blue).
LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(1.0f, Color.
    BLUE);

15 // This tutorial uses a data set
// constructor that associates a marker and
// line styles with the data set.
// Note that you can avoid providing a
// marker style when a line style is given
// (DataSet dataSet = DataSet.getFor2D
// ("Test data set", data, ls)); the
// markers will not be drawn then (the line
// will be drawn if there are at least
// two connected points).
20 DataSet dataSet = DataSet.getFor2D("Test
    data set", data, ms, ls);
plot.getModel().setDataSet(dataSet, true);
```

3.5. Introducing breaks into rendered lines [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t5

The following tutorial explains how breaks can be introduced into lines (by default, the lines are continuous). As explained in Section 2.4, a null entry has to be added to the *LinkedList<double[][]>* raw data object in order to introduce a break into the line (break will be introduced between the

neighboring `double[][]` data segments). The relevant code snippet from this tutorial is presented in Listing 10, and the expected plot is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: A simple data set represented as a line with a break

Listing 10: Creating a line with a break

```

double [][] line1 = new double [][]
{
    { 0.0d, 0.0},
    { 0.25d, 0.25d},
};

double [][] line2 = new double [][]
{
    {0.5d, 0.5d},
    {0.75d, 0.25d},
    {1.0d, 1.0d},
};

// Raw data can be provided in chunks (
// double[][]) aggregated in a LinkedList.
// The default painter objects
// responsible for rendering assume that
// nulls added to the list serve as
// breaking points between two chunks
// interpreted as lines. If you comment out
// the "data.add(null);" line, the data
// set will be rendered without the break.
LinkedList<double [][]> data = new
LinkedList<>();
data.add(line1);
data.add(null); // comment out this line to
// avoid the break
data.add(line2);

```

3.6. Establishing a custom display ranges mapping [T]

Source package:
`t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t6`

As explained in Section 2.3, the display ranges manager allows the creation of custom mappings, which may prove helpful when the data is in nonstandard form and one wants to avoid making redundant transformations. This tutorial provides a simple example of introducing custom mapping when establishing the display ranges manager params container. The assumption is that the input data points take the following form: [Y-coordinate-related attribute, irrelevant attribute, X-coordinate-related attribute]. The essential parts of this source are provided in Listing 11 and the expected output in Figure 8.

Figure 8: A plot with a custom display ranges mapping

Listing 11: Creating a custom mapping

```

// Create a display ranges manager (params
// container).
pp._pDisplayRangesManager = new
DisplayRangesManager.Params();
pp._pDisplayRangesManager._DR = new
DisplayRangesManager.DisplayRange[2];
// The display range for the X and Y axes
// is set to null with a dynamic update
// flag turned on.
pp._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[0] = new
DisplayRangesManager.DisplayRange(null,
true);
pp._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[1] = new
DisplayRangesManager.DisplayRange(null,
true);
// The follow line constructs attribute-
// display range mapping. It states that
// the first attribute should be

```

```

// mapped into the Y-axis (index of 1), the
// second attribute should be ignored (
// null), and the last attribute
// should be linked to the X-axis (index of
// 0). Note that the indexes in the below
// array should be from a set
10 // {0, 1,...,n}, where n denotes the number
// of display ranges considered. Their
// validity will be checked when
// instantiating the display ranges manager
// (simple assertion).
pP._pDisplayRangesManager._attIdx_to_drIdx
    = new Integer[]{1, null, 0};

[...]

15 // The input data points provided below are
// organized as follows: the first
// attribute that should be mapped
// into Y-axis, the second attribute that
// is irrelevant, and the third attribute
// that should be mapped into X-axis.
double[][] data = new double[][]
{
20     {0.0d, 100.0d, 0.0d},
     {0.25d, -5.0d, 0.5d},
     {0.5d, 99.0d, 0.75d},
     {2.0d, 15.0d, 1.0d}
};

```


Figure 9: A plot with multiple data sets and a legend

3.7. Using multiple data sets and enabling the legend [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1.visualization.module.t1_plot2d.t7

The visualization tool allows the displaying of multiple data sets along with the legend. These data sets can be provided via ArrayList. Regarding the legend, it must be enabled via the plot params container (`_drawLegend` flag), and it automatically builds its content based on data set names and marker/line styles. Listing 12 provides relevant code snippets from this tutorial, while the expected result is presented in Figure 9.

Listing 12: Using multiple data sets and legend

```

// The following flag has to be set to true
// to enable legend rendering. Note that
// the legend entries will be
// automatically specified based on the
// data sets being maintained by the plot.
pP._drawLegend = true;

5 [...]

// The data sets should be stored in an
// array list
ArrayList<IDataSet> dataSets = new
    ArrayList<>(2);

10 { // The following block creates the first
// data set (blue line)
// blue line
double[][] data = new double[][]
{
    {0.0d, 1.0d},
    {1.0d, 0.0d},
};
LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(1.0f, Color.
    BLUE);
dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor2D("DS1", data
    , ls));

20 }
{ // The following block creates the second
// data set (red dots)
// red points
double[][] data = new double[][]
{
25     {0.0d, 0.0d},
     {0.5d, 0.5d},
     {1.0d, 1.0d}
};
// Line style can also be used as a
// marker edge style (see lines below).
LineStyle mes = new LineStyle(1.0f, Color
    .BLACK);
MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(5.0f,
    Color.RED, Marker.CIRCLE, mes);
ataSets.add(DataSet.getFor2D("DS2", data,
    ms));

30 }

35 plot.getModel().setDataSets(dataSets, true)
;

```

3.8. Customizing the legend [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t8

The current version of the framework allows only a simple customization of the legend. The scheme object (*scheme.AbstractScheme*) provided via the plot params container can adjust such properties as the font name, size, margins, or alignment. Further, as discussed in Section 2.4, the legend entries can be turned off (or data set rendering), which can be helpful when implementing an out-of-the-box plot. This tutorial example explains these parameterization means. The most relevant code snippets from this executable are provided in Listing 13, while the expected output is in Figure 10.

Figure 10: A plot with a customized legend

Listing 13: Customizing the legend

```
pP._drawLegend = true;
// The legend can be customized by
// adjusting selected fields in the scheme
// object. The below three lines set
// the legend background to a light gray
// and place it outside the plot area (
// right/top position). Additionally,
// the right plot margin is extended to fit
// the legend.
pP._scheme = new WhiteScheme();
pP._scheme._align.put(AlignFields.LEGEND,
    Align.RIGHT_TOP_EXTERNAL);
pP._scheme._color.put(ColorFields.
    LEGEND_BACKGROUND, new color.Color(0.8f,
    0.8f, 0.8f));
pP._scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
    MARGIN_RIGHT_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER,
    0.175f);
```

```
// This tutorial creates 5 data sets. The
// first two are renderable, and their
// legend entries are displayable.
// The third data set is renderable, but
// its legend entry is not displayable. The
// fourth data set uses the
// opposite properties. The last data set
// is neither renderable nor has a
// displayable legend entry.
ArrayList<IDataSet> dataSets = new
    ArrayList<>(2);
{
    // renderable and entry legend
    // displayable
    double[][] data = new double[][]
    {
        {0.0d, 1.0d},
        {1.0d, 0.0d},
    };
    LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(1.0f, Color.
        BLUE);
    dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor2D("DS1", data
        , ls));
}
{
    // renderable and entry legend
    // displayable
    double[][] data = new double[][]
    {
        {0.0d, 0.0d},
        {0.5d, 0.5d},
        {1.0d, 1.0d}
    };
    LineStyle mes = new LineStyle(1.0f, Color
        .BLACK);
    MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(5.0f,
        Color.RED, Marker.CIRCLE, mes);
    dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor2D("DS2", data
        , ms));
}
{
    // renderable but entry legend is not
    // displayable
    double[][] data = new double[][]
    {
        {0.25d, 0.75d},
        {0.5d, 0.75d},
        {0.75d, 0.75d};
    };
    MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(5.0f,
        Color.GREEN, Marker.SQUARE);
    DataSet ds = DataSet.getFor2D("DS3", data
        , ms);
    // Set "displayable on legend" flag to
    // false (disables legend entry rendering
    // )
    ds.setDisplayableOnLegend(false);
    dataSets.add(ds);
}
{
    // not renderable but entry legend is
    // displayable
```

```

double[][] data = new double[][]{}; //
    data is not needed
LineStyle edge = new LineStyle(1.0f,
    Color.BLACK);
MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(5.0f,
    Color.BLUE, Marker.TRIANGLE_UP, edge);
DataSet ds = DataSet.getFor2D("DS4", data
    , ms);
55 // Set 'skip rendering' flag to true (
    disables data set rendering; but
    legend entry will be rendered)
ds.setSkipRendering(true);
dataSets.add(ds);
}
{
60 // not renderable and entry legend is not
    displayable
double[][] data = new double[][]{}; //
    data is not needed
MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(5.0f,
    Color.BLACK, Marker.TRIANGLE_DOWN);
DataSet ds = DataSet.getFor2D("DS5", data
    , ms);
// Set 'displayable on legend' flag to
    false (disables legend entry rendering
    )
65 ds.setDisplayableOnLegend(false);
// Set 'skip rendering' flag to true (
    disables data set rendering)
ds.setSkipRendering(true);
dataSets.add(ds);
}
70 plot.getModel().setDataSets(dataSets, true)
    ;

```

3.9. Using gradients [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t9

This tutorial focuses on using gradient to color illustrated data sets. Before proceeding, it is worth highlighting that the gradients impose much more significant computational and memory costs than when using mono-colors. There are two reasons for that:

- When using a mono-color, no additional color-related data is generated or stored. A color is explicitly derived from the provided marker/line style and set as active before executing draw methods. In contrast, when a gradient is used, a suitable color is predetermined for each data point in a data set and stored in the memory. Thus, the more points, the more calculations and memory space will be required. For instance, for 3D rendering, no additional color buffer is created when using a mono-color. The use of a gradient will imply submitting such a buffer.
- The use of a gradient is exceptionally costly when rendering lines. Imagine that two very distant data points

are to be connected with a gradient line. By default, linear color interpolation would be used to determine colors for the intermediate points, but it could ultimately not match the gradient provided along with the line style (due to, e.g., non-linearity). To resolve this problem, the visualization tool, in this case, will construct physically many intermediate points and store them along with the original ones. A valid gradient color will also be determined and stored for all these points. During the rendering step, each pair of neighboring points will be connected with a mono-color line, but since there will be many densely located points, it will produce a gradient. Nonetheless, creating many such auxiliary points will negatively affect both memory and computational complexity. Note that the density of these points can be controlled by adjusting the `'_gradientLineMinSegmentLength'` field of `dataset.painter.AbstractPainter` class.

This tutorial provides a brief example of how to use gradients. First, it is worth noting that a gradient consists of a mapping that associates normalized values from 0 to 1 with a color (a color for a value between two provided points is interpolated linearly from the linked neighboring colors). Second, a gradient must be bounded with one display range (index). When a color for a data point is to be determined, the system first identifies the relevant attribute ID linked to the display range associated with the gradient. Then, the normalized attributed value of the data point is obtained (from 0 to 1), and finally, a gradient color is derived for this normalized value.

The example in this tutorial involves two data sets, each colored using a gradient. The first data set is a line colored using a Viridis gradient. The color is determined based on the X-coordinate (the first display range, index of 0). The next data set illustrates points (Marker.CIRCLE) whose fill and edge colors are derived from a gradient. When it comes to the fill color, an Inferno gradient is used, and the color is determined based on the point's normalized Y-coordinate, whereas the edge color is picked from the red-blue gradient (based on the normalized X-coordinate). The relevant code snippet from this example is provided in Listing 14, and the expected output is in Figure 11.

Listing 14: Creating data sets colored using a gradient

```

{
double[][] data = new double[][]
{
    {0.0d, 1.0d},
    {1.0d, 0.0d},
};
5 // The line can be colored using a
    gradient. The following constructor
    creates a line style that uses a
// Viridis gradient. Furthermore, the
    gradient color is determined using the
    first attribute value. The
// provided zero index specifies a
    connection between the gradient and
    the first (zeroth) display range
// in the display range manager. This
    connection is used, e.g., to derive

```


Figure 11: A simple plot using gradients to color data sets

```

    the normalization function from
// the display range to accordingly map
the attribute value into value in the
[0, 1] bound (the gradient
// object maps a [0, 1] value into a
color). Note that an error may occur
if the display range at the
// specified index does not exist.
LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(1.0f,
    Gradient.getViridisGradient(), 0);
dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor2D("DS1", data
    , ls));
}
{
double [][] data = new double [][]
{
    {0.0d, 0.0d},
    {0.5d, 0.5d},
    {1.0d, 1.0d}
};

// Markers can also be colored using a
gradient (it is also true for their
edges). This can be achieved
// similarly to how a gradient for the
line was specified (the following
lines bound the marker edge gradient
// (red-blue) and the marker fill
gradient (inferno) with the second
display range).
LineStyle mes = new LineStyle(1.0f,
    Gradient.getRedBlueGradient(), 1);
MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(5.0f,
    Gradient.getInfernoGradient(), 1,
    Marker.CIRCLE, mes);

```

```

dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor2D("DS2", data
    , ms));
}

```

3.10. Gradient customization [T]

Source package:

`t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t10`

This tutorial discusses versatile means for gradient customization. It emphasizes that a gradient object is not a rigid structure but a flexible entity with two major fields: the value-color mappings and an interpolation flag. This flexibility allows you to control the behavior of the gradient. For instance, if the interpolation flag is true, the colors not specified in the map are interpolated linearly based on the closest surrounding value-color mappings. If false, the closest mapping is returned instead. This means that you have the power to produce a discretized gradient if the number of mappings is low and the flag is false.

Understanding the trade-off between the gradient color fidelity and the computational/memory costs is crucial. This knowledge empowers you to make informed decisions about your visualization. On one side of the spectrum, the lowest costs are imposed when the number of mappings is small, and the interpolation flag is false. Turning off the interpolation will not produce additional color objects, as the gradient color will return references to kept colors only when asked for color (the enabled flag will return new color instances each time requested). Conversely, the highest fidelity and costs will be achieved when the number of mappings is substantial, and the interpolation flag is true. To reach a satisfactory trade-off, it is recommended to turn off the interpolation flag and use a reasonably large number of mappings (e.g., 256 uniformly distributed colors).

The source code demonstrates the flexibility of various parameterizations by constructing four Viridis gradients (interpolation flag true/false; low/high number of mappings). It also shows how you can build a new gradient by providing color tables or assignments, allowing for non-uniformly distributed values. The code snippets provided in Listing 15 show how to customize a gradient, while the expected output is showcased in Figure 12 (order of legend entries explicitly matches the order of rendered data sets, i.e., from top to bottom).

Listing 15: Creating custom gradients

```

// The gradient colors for pre-defined
gradients are tabularized (see classes
in color.gradient.gradients).
// The below line retrieves colors for the
Viridis gradient (256 uniformly
distributed colors defined as
// [0-1] RGB tuples). This array will be
used later to construct custom gradients
.
float [][] colors = Viridis.colors;
{

```


Figure 12: A plot illustrating six custom gradients

```

double [][] data = new double [][]
{
    {0.0d, 0.6d},
    {1.0d, 0.6d},
};

// A gradient object consists of two
// primary fields: associations between
// the normalized [0-1] value and
// a color (see color.gradient.
// ColorAssignment; the normalized values
// are kept sorted in an ascending order
// );
// and an interpolation flag. The
// interpolation flag is used when
// retrieving a color for which the input
// normalized value is not stored. If the
// flag is true, the nearest normalized
// values to the requested one
// are identified (smaller/equal and
// greater/equal; binary search is used)
// and their associated colors.
// Then, a new color (object) whose RGB
// values are linearly interpolated is
// constructed and returned.
// However, if the flag is false, the
// already kept object, a color whose
// value is the closest to the
// requested one, is returned. The former
// option is not recommended as it may
// end with constructing
// an enormous number of new objects on
// the fly. The latter object is
// preferred, but the number of

```

```

// pre-defined colors stored in the
// gradient must be reasonably large (e.g
// ., 256).

// The below line constructs a gradient
// that consists of 256 colors derived
// from the input color table
// and with an interpolation flag set to
// false. It is the recommended option
// for custom gradient construction
// (high fidelity, low computational
// burden, and low memory consumption).
Gradient gradient = Gradient.
    getGradientFromColorMatrix(colors, "
    Viridis (256; no interpolation)", 256,
    false);
LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(4.0f,
    gradient, 0);
dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor2D("Viridis
    (256; no interpolation)", data, ls));
}
{
    double [][] data = new double [][]
    {
        {0.0d, 0.5d},
        {1.0d, 0.5d},
    };
    // This setting differs from the previous
    // one in terms of the number of stored
    // colors (the four colors
    // stored are four colors in the input
    // color table that are most equally
    // spaced, under the assumption of
    // a uniform distribution of associated
    // values). Since the interpolation mode
    // is off, reducing the number
    // of colors will result in gradient
    // discretization.
    Gradient gradient = Gradient.
        getGradientFromColorMatrix(colors, "
        Viridis (16; no interpolation)", 16,
        false);
    LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(4.0f,
        gradient, 0);
    dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor2D("Viridis
        (16; no interpolation)", data, ls));
}
{
    double [][] data = new double [][]
    {
        {0.0d, 0.4d},
        {1.0d, 0.4d},
    };
    // This setting uses 3 tabularized colors
    // , but the interpolation is enabled.
    // The latter implies that there
    // will be no gradient discretization
    // this time. However, since the number
    // of stored colors is deficient,
    // the color fidelity will be diminished
    // (the resulting gradient will slightly
    // differ from the expected one,

```

```

// i.e., as there would be an infinite
// number of input colors spanned on the
// [0-1] value interval).
Gradient gradient = Gradient.
getGradientFromColorMatrix(colors, "
  Viridis (3; interpolation)", 3, true);
LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(4.0f,
  gradient, 0);
dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor2D("Viridis
  (3; interpolation)", data, ls));
}
{
double[][] data = new double[][]
{
  {0.0d, 0.3d},
  {1.0d, 0.3d},
};
// The fourth setting is of the
// highest fidelity but also imposes
// the highest computational (and
// memory)
// burden (there are many pre-defined
// color assignments, and the
// requested colors should be
// interpolated).
Gradient gradient = Gradient.
getGradientFromColorMatrix(colors,
  "Viridis (256; interpolation)",
  256, true);
LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(4.0f,
  gradient, 0);
dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor2D("
  Viridis (256; interpolation)",
  data, ls));
}
{
double[][] data = new double[][]
{
  {0.0d, 0.2d},
  {1.0d, 0.2d},
};
// The next setting shows how to create a
// custom gradient from a custom color
// table (4 colors, interpolation).
// Note that the table's entries are in
// the RGBA format (0-1 floats).
float [][] myColors = new float [][]
{
  {0.0f, 0.0f, 0.0f, 1.0f}, // black
  {0.0f, 0.0f, 1.0f, 1.0f}, // blue
  {1.0f, 0.0f, 0.0f, 1.0f}, // red
  {0.0f, 1.0f, 0.0f, 1.0f} // green
};
Gradient gradient = Gradient.
getGradientFromColorMatrix(myColors, "
  My gradient #1 (4; interpolation)", 4,
  true);
LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(4.0f,
  gradient, 0);
dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor2D("My

```

```

  gradient #1 (4; interpolation)", data,
  ls));
}
{
double[][] data = new double[][]
{
  {0.0d, 0.1d},
  {1.0d, 0.1d},
};
// The last setting shows how to create a
// custom gradient from color
// assignments (4 colors, interpolation).
// Note that the colors are in the RGBA
// format (0-1 floats).
ArrayList<ColorAssignment> cas = new
  ArrayList<>();
cas.add(new ColorAssignment(0.0f, new
  Color(0.0f, 0.0f, 0.0f, 1.0f)));
cas.add(new ColorAssignment(0.2f, new
  Color(0.0f, 0.0f, 1.0f, 1.0f)));
cas.add(new ColorAssignment(0.8f, new
  Color(1.0f, 0.0f, 0.0f, 1.0f)));
cas.add(new ColorAssignment(1.0f, new
  Color(0.0f, 1.0f, 0.0f, 1.0f)));
Gradient gradient = new Gradient(cas, "My
  gradient #2 (4; interpolation)",
  true);
LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(4.0f,
  gradient, 0);
dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor2D("My
  gradient #2 (4; interpolation)", data,
  ls));
}

```

3.11. Creating a colorbar and using a non-coordinate-dependent gradient [T]

Source package:

`t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t11`

This tutorial focuses on two aspects: adding a colorbar to the plot and using a gradient to perform not-coordinate-dependent coloring. These are real-world scenarios that you, as a data visualization practitioner, programmer, or researcher, are likely to encounter in your work.

Consider the following scenario: there are n points whose X and Y coordinates are drawn randomly from a Gaussian distribution (mean of 0 and standard deviation of 0.25). The goal is to color these points based on their distances to the plot origin, i.e., (0, 0) point. Apart from imposing such a coloring procedure, a suitably adjusted colorbar has to be added to the plot.

The source code includes the creation of a third display range (see the essential code snippets in Listing 16), in addition to the standard two display ranges specified (with a fixed range [-1; 1], linked to the X and Y axis). This third range is associated with data point distance, which can be considered its attribute.

The code sets the initial range to null but allows for dynamic updates, providing flexibility in the visualization of the data.

Next, the code establishes a colorbar instance (an object provided via the plot params container). To create the colorbar object, two essential objects must be delivered (apart from the title): a gradient and an implementation of an *ITicksDataGetter* interface. The latter is an auxiliary object responsible for providing data on the axis's ticks (a colorbar possesses its own axis). The implementation used in this source code is "FromDisplayRange," which serves as a binding to one of the display range objects maintained by the display ranges manager. This way, the colorbar can automatically determine the bounds for the display range (associated with data points' distances) and, thus, create proper tick labels.

Lastly, the input data points must include the information on the distance. Therefore, the points are defined by three attributes: X-coordinate, Y-coordinate, and the distance (a square root of X squared plus Y squared). Note that that the marker style is linked the third display range (distances) to properly use the provided gradient object.

The final plot is illustrated in Figures 13 (continuous gradient was used) and 14 (discrete gradient was used).

Figure 13: A plot using a color bar and a continuous gradient

Listing 16: Creating a colorbar and using a non-coordinate-dependent gradient

```
// Let's first create a display range
// manager (params container). The lines
// below establish three display
// ranges: for the X axis, for the Y axis,
// and an auxiliary display range
// associated with the data point
// distance to the (0, 0) coordinate. While
// the first two are fixed and set to [-1,
// 1] ranges, the last is
// dynamic and initially nulled.
```


Figure 14: A plot using a color bar and a discrete gradient

```
5 pP._pDisplayRangesManager = new
  DisplayRangesManager.Params();
pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR = new
  DisplayRangesManager.DisplayRange[3];
pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[0] = new
  DisplayRangesManager.DisplayRange(new
  Range(-1.0d, 1.0d), false);
pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[1] = new
  DisplayRangesManager.DisplayRange(new
  Range(-1.0d, 1.0d), false);
pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[2] = new
  DisplayRangesManager.DisplayRange(null,
  true);
10 [...]

// A colorbar object requires providing an
// auxiliary object that implements an
// ITicksDataGetter interface
// responsible for creating ticks (and
// their positions and associated values).
// The implementation below can be
// considered binding between the colorbar
// axis and a selected display range (the
// third one).
ITicksDataGetter tdg = new FromDisplayRange
  (pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[2], 10);

// This line provides a colorbar to the
// plot params container (gradient object,
// title, and the ticks data getter).
pP._colorbar = new Colorbar(gradient, "
  Distance", tdg);

pP._scheme = new WhiteScheme();
// We need to extend the margin so that the
```

```

        colorbar can fit.
    pP._scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
        MARGIN_RIGHT_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER,
        0.25f);
[...]

// The lines below create data consisting
// of a selected number of data points.
// Each data point has three
// attributes: random x and y coordinates (
// drawn randomly from a Gaussian
// distribution with a standard
// deviation of 0.25) and a distance from
// the drawn coordinates to the [0,0]
// coordinate.
int noSamples = 100000;
IRandom R = new MersenneTwister64(0);
double[][] data = new double[noSamples][3];
for (int i = 0; i < noSamples; i++)
{
    double x = R.nextGaussian() * 0.25d;
    double y = R.nextGaussian() * 0.25d;
    double d = Math.sqrt(x * x + y * y);
    data[i][0] = x;
    data[i][1] = y;
    data[i][2] = d;
}

// The marker style definition binds the
// constructed gradient object with the
// third display range
// (associated with the data points'
// distances to the plot center).
MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(1.0f,
    gradient, 2, Marker.CIRCLE);
IDataSet dataSet = DataSet.getFor2D("Random
    points", data, ms);

```

3.12. Turning off drawing area clipping [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t12

By default, rendering is clipped to the main drawing area. The clipping can be turned off by modifying a single flag in the params container (see Listing 17). This example is founded on the previous one (Section 3.11). Here, a standard deviation of the Gaussian distribution was increased to 0.3 to force more points to land outside the $[-1, 1]^2$ fixed bounds. The expected plot is illustrated in Figure 15.

Listing 17: Turning off drawing area clipping

```

// Can be turned off to allow rendering
// outside the drawing area
pP._clipDrawingArea = false;

```


Figure 15: A plot with clipping turned off

3.13. Examining marker style configurations [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t13

The following brief tutorial examines various marker style configurations (shapes, fill colors, edge styles). There was no reason to bring any code snippet here as this source code is as simple as it can be. Figure 16 depicts the expected plot where data points are organized in rows, where each row examines all shapes, but rows differ in general configuration. What is worth noting and new is that the colors can be supplied with the alpha channel (RGBA 0-1 floats format), and the plot drawing area supports transparency (see the second row, counting from the bottom, where the markers opacity transits from near zero to 1). However, the transparency per se is not optimized in the visualization tool. Hence, it may slow processing and occasionally produce glitches (e.g., when rendering line joints).

3.14. Using nonlinear scales [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t14

This tutorial teaches how to use nonlinear scales, reconfigure axes, and re-position grid lines. First, consider the **Tutorial14a source code** in the tutorial package. It creates a simple data set of a series of connected points rapidly decreasing at first but flattening later. The coordinates were derived using a formula provided in Listing 18, and the expected plot is illustrated in Figure 17. Note that a gradient was used to distinguish between Y-coordinates. Notably, this plot's readability is poor because the convergence curve is extremely pushed toward the left-bottom corner of the plot.

Figure 16: A plot exhibiting various marker style configurations

Figure 17: The default plot

Listing 18: Input data

```

int n = 100;
double [][] data = new double[n][2];
for (int i = 0; i < n; i++)
{
    data[i][0] = (double) i / (n - 1);
    data[i][1] = 1.0d / (double) (i + 1);
}

```

Customizing the normalization process. **Tutorial14b** code shows how to resolve the readability issue introduced in **Tutorial14a**. For this reason, it redefines the normalization function associated with the Y-axis. As explained in Sections 2.1 and 2.3, a display range object handles a normalization function that transforms input data points into normalized points. This function is, by default, set to a simple min-max linear interpolation. One can replace this function with another one to change the scale used with a particular dimension.

This tutorial uses a gamma normalization instead of the linear one, i.e., the following formula is used: $[(value - min) / (max - min)]^\gamma$, where γ is the power index. A code snippet in listing 19 shows how this function can be assigned to the Y-axis (the second display range; a gamma coefficient of 0.25 is used). The resulting plot with a nonlinear Y-dimension is depicted in Figure 18. **Important note: The normalization process only affects the data points.** It will not affect a line connecting them if a line style is used (the line will remain straight).

Figure 18: Plot with altered scale of the Y-dimension

Listing 19: Changing the normalization function associated with the Y-dimension

```

// Create default params with fixed normal
// ranges.
pP._pDisplayRangesManager =
    DisplayRangesManager.Params.getFor2D(
        Range.getNormalRange(), Range.
        getNormalRange());

// A display range can be supplied with a
// normalizer (min-max based) responsible
// for mapping the original
// coordinate values into normalized space.
// The line below specifies that the Y-
// coordinate (the second display

```

```

// range) should be normalized using gamma
// normalization. This normalizer first
// interpolates the original
// values into [0, 1] space and then uses a
// gamma transformation ([0, 1] value
// raised to the selected power).
// This example uses a power of 0.25 to ‘‘
// straighten the plot’’. Important note:
// only the input data points are
// normalized. If a line style is used,
// straight lines will be drawn between the
// normalized points, but the
// lines will not be adjusted (bent).
pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[1].
    setNormalizer(new Gamma(0.25d));

```

Adjusting grids and customizing axes' ticks. While the plot generated in **Tutorial14b** is now more readable, the Y-axis's ticks are not. They remain in the same positions in the normalized [0-1] space, but their associated values become abnormal due to using a different normalization function (although they are correct, of course). **Tutorial14c** shows how to adjust tick locations and labels. It also shows how to adjust grid lines to match new tick positions and reveals how to use a different number format for tick labels or provide custom, pre-defined labels (e.g., strings). Overall, the changes done in this tutorial are as follows:

- Ticks for the Y-axis and the colorbar axis are adjusted to point to the following values: 0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0.
- The Y-axis and the color bar axis use decimal format instead of a scientific one.
- The horizontal lines of the main and auxiliary grids are adjusted. The lines of the main grid now align with the Y-axis ticks, while the lines of the auxiliary grid point exactly between them (i.e., to the following values: 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9).
- The tick labels of the X-axis are now custom strings: ‘‘A’’, ‘‘B’’, ‘‘C’’, ‘‘D’’, ‘‘E’’.

The code snippet that exhibits and discusses the adjustments made is in Listing 20, while the resulting plot is illustrated in Figure 19.

Listing 20: Customizing axes and grid lines

```

// Number format is associated with a ticks
// data getter and can be provided in the
// following way (for colorbar):
NumberFormat numberFormat = new
    DecimalFormat();
ITicksDataGetter tdg = new FromDisplayRange
    (pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[1], 5,
    numberFormat);
pP._colorbar = new Colorbar(gradient, "Y-
    value", tdg);
[...]

```


Figure 19: Plot with adjusted axes and grid lines

```

// Now, imagine that we want the ticks of
// the Y-axis to be precisely located at
// [0, 0.2, 0.4,...,1] values. The
// ticks' locations (and labels) can be
// customized only after the plot is
// instantiated. To access plot
// components, one has to use plot.
// getComponentsContainer(). The container
// stores references to various plot
// components (and provides various getters
// ). We can use it to access the Y-axis
// via retrieving the axes array
// (getAxes()) and the element under the
// index of 1 (y-axis). The received object
// is an extension of
// component.axis.AbstractAxis and provides
// a getter to an implementation of
// ITicksDataGetter. We can use its
// 'setForcedUnnormalizedLocations' to
// specify an array of tick locations in
// the before-normalized space (they
// will directly point to expected values).
// Similarly, a method called '
// setForcedUnnormalizedLocations' will
// allow the adjustment of the ticks'
// locations in the normalized space (they
// will point to desired [0-1]
// normalized positions).
plot.getComponentsContainer().getAxes()[1].
    getTicksDataGetter().
    setForcedNormalizedLocations(
    new float[]{0.0f, 0.2f, 0.4f, 0.6f, 0.8f,
    1.0f});
// Let's do the same but for the colorbar:
plot.getComponentsContainer().getColorbar()

```

```

    .getAxis().getTicksDataGetter().
    setForcedUnnormalizedLocations(
new float []{0.0f, 0.2f, 0.4f, 0.6f, 0.8f,
1.0f});

// The ticks data getter also allows
    providing custom (non-numerical; data
    independent labels):
25 plot.getComponentsContainer().getAxes()[0].
    getTicksDataGetter().
    setPredefinedTickLabels(
new String[]{"A", "B", "C", "D", "E"});

// Number format can be established in the
    following way (for Y-axis):
30 plot.getComponentsContainer().getAxes()[1].
    getTicksDataGetter().setNumberFormat(
    numberFormat);

// The following lines intend to adjust the
    positions of the grid lines (only the
    horizontal lines that should
    // be associated with the Y-axis's ticks).
    First, we need to derive the drawing
    area component:
DrawingArea2D drawingArea = (DrawingArea2D)
    plot.getComponentsContainer().
    getDrawingArea();

35 // Next, there are two types of grid
    components: the main grid and the
    auxiliary. Both can be customized. In
    // this case, the position adjustment
    process can also rely on a ticks data
    getter. The following four lines
    // specify appropriate tick data getters
    for the main and auxiliary grid and
    establish the (unnormalized) ticks'
    // locations.
drawingArea.getMainGrid().
    setHorizontalTicksDataGetter(new
    FromDisplayRange(pP.
    _pDisplayRangesManager._DR[1], 6));
40 drawingArea.getMainGrid().
    getHorizontalTicksDataGetter().
    setForcedUnnormalizedLocations(new float
    []{0.0f, 0.2f, 0.4f, 0.6f, 0.8f, 1.0f});

drawingArea.getAuxGrid().
    setHorizontalTicksDataGetter(new
    FromDisplayRange(pP.
    _pDisplayRangesManager._DR[1], 5));
drawingArea.getAuxGrid().
    getHorizontalTicksDataGetter().
    setForcedUnnormalizedLocations(new float
    []{0.1f, 0.3f, 0.5f, 0.7f, 0.9f});

```

Finally, consider **Tutorial14d**. It differs from **Tutorial14c** in that it uses a logarithmic scale instead of gamma. Although the alternation can be achieved easily (see code snippet in Listing 21), it is worth remembering that calculating a logarithm

from 0 (or negative values) brings ill results (undefined). Therefore, one should avoid defining an improper domain when establishing display ranges (or providing incompatible data). Unfortunately, the current framework version will not automatically adjust ticks. You must do it manually based on the selected logarithmic base, as presented in Listing 21). The expected plot is illustrated in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Plot with adjusted axes and grid lines (logarithmic scale)

Listing 21: Customizing axes and grid lines

```

pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[1].
    setNormalizer(new Logarithmic());
[...]
plot.getComponentsContainer().getAxes()[1].
    getTicksDataGetter().
    setForcedUnnormalizedLocations(new float
    []{1.0f / 32.0f, 1.0f / 16.0f, 1.0f /
    8.0f, 1.0f / 4.0f, 1.0f / 2.0f, 1.0f});

```

4. General plot for 3D visualization

This section introduces a 3D visualization plot (*plot.Plot3D*). Fortunately, it was built mainly on general and common components shared with *Plot2D*, so the utilization of both plots is almost identical. Consequently, this section is much shorter than the previous one to avoid repetitions.

Before proceeding, it is worth highlighting that *Plot3D* has a built-in interaction functionality. Specifically, if the plot is active (becomes active after clicking), the following projection manipulations can be performed via mouse and keyboard:

- Mouse left-click dragging: changing the camera orientation.
- Mouse right-click dragging: changing the plot orientation.

- ‘w’ (‘s’) key pressed: the camera moves forward (backward) as imposed by the current camera orientation.
- ‘a’ (‘d’) key pressed: the camera moves left (right) as imposed by the current camera orientation.
- ‘q’ (‘e’) key pressed: the camera moves up (down) (independently of camera orientation; moving up is relative to the horizontal plane spanned on the X and Z axes.
- ‘r’ key pressed: resets the projection.

4.1. Creating and displaying a plot [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t2_plot3d.t1

The source code in Tutorial1a showcases how one can create a plot for 3D visualization and display it. The code is as simple as it can be (see Listing 22; note the `WhiteScheme.getForPlot3D()` method used to create a suitably adjusted white scheme), and, as explained before, the API is similar to a large extent to those of *Plot2D*. The final (expected) window is presented in Figure 21. At this point, it is worth examining the possible interactions with the plot (mouse + keyboard).

Figure 21: The expected window containing the empty plot

Listing 22: Creating and displaying a plot 3D

```
//Create the params container for 3D plot.
Plot3D.Params pP = new Plot3D.Params();

// Create a default display ranges manager
// (params container) for plot 3D.
// The first display ranges are reserved
// for the X, Y, and Z axes, respectively.
```

```
// The known ranges are set to null but
// updated dynamically each time a new
// dataset is uploaded.
pP._pDisplayRangesManager =
    DisplayRangesManager.Params.getFor3D();

pP._title = "Tutorial 1";
pP._xAxisTitle = "X-axis";
pP._yAxisTitle = null; // the label will
// not be displayed
pP._zAxisTitle = "Z-axis";

// This method returns a white scheme that
// is suitably customized for plot 3d (no
// margins, no drawing area border)
pP._scheme = WhiteScheme.getForPlot3D();

// Create the plot object:
Plot3D plot = new Plot3D(pP);
Frame.Params pF = Frame.Params.getParams(
    plot, 0.5f);
pF._title = "Window title";
Frame frame = new Frame(pF);
frame.setVisible(true);
```

The general Tutorial 0 (overview) explains that these documents will not cover everything. It is up to the programmer to examine code possibilities. For instance, exploring the `Params` class (if provided) and its Javadoc comments is recommended. Listing 23 provides a brief snippet of `Plot3D.Params` class, where various useful customization options can be found. The source code in **Tutorial1b** (see Listing 24) showcases how one can creatively adjust the plot setup. First, it specifies that the drawing area borders will not be rendered. Second, it defines only the bottom pane to be used (a pane is an object containing a grid). Third, it fixes the position of the X, Y, and Z axes (note that each axis can appear multiple times in up to four compatible locations on the edges of the drawing area). Lastly, the code shows how to extend the drawing area along the X-dimension. Such a customized plot is depicted in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Plot with adjusted panes, axes, and bounds

Listing 23: Plot 3D params container

```

[...]
/**
 * Panes to be drawn (expressed as a list
   of their alignments; default = LEFT,
   BACK, BOTTOM).
 */
5 public Align[] _paneAlignments = new Align
  []{Align.BOTTOM, Align.RIGHT, Align.BACK
    };

/**
 * axes to be drawn (expressed as a list of
   their alignments; can be null).
 */
10 public Align[] _axesAlignments = new Align
  []{Align.FRONT_BOTTOM, Align.BACK_RIGHT,
    Align.LEFT_TOP};

/**
 * Determines the number of offscreen
   buffers used for rendering on the GPU.
 * Recommended = 2. Note that the painting
   is asynchronous and, thus, if = 1,
15 * the tearing may be substantial.
 */
public int _noBuffers = 3;

/**
20 * If true, the main plot area will be
   outlined with a cuboid.
 */
public boolean _drawCube = true;
[...]
/**
25 * Projection bound for the x-dimension (if
   null, default values are used, i.e., [
   position = -0.5; size = 1.0].
 */
public Dimension _xProjectionBound = null;
[...]

```

Listing 24: Plot 3D layout customization

```

// Disable the 3D drawing area outline
pP._drawCube = false;
// Specify that only the bottom pane will
  be rendered.
pP._paneAlignments = new Align[]{Align.
  BOTTOM};
5
// Specify alignments for 3D axes. Note
  that the alignments can be provided
  arbitrarily; the axis-alignment
// matching will be done automatically.
  Additionally, multiple (i.e., more than
  1) alignments that match
// a particular axis type (e.g., X-axis)
  can be specified. If so, multiple such
  axes will be drawn. In this
// example, the matching axes are as
  follows: Y-axis (BACK_RIGHT), X-axis (
  FRONT_TOP), and two Z-axes

```

```

10 // (LEFT_BOTTOM and RIGHT_TOP). Note that
   using ‘‘draw axis’’ flag has no effect.
pP._axesAlignments = new Align[]{Align.
  BACK_RIGHT, Align.FRONT_TOP, Align.
  LEFT_BOTTOM, Align.RIGHT_TOP};

// The plot drawing area is spanned on
  [-0.5, 0.5] bound by default. These
  bounds can be, however, customized.
// The line below resizes the drawing area
  long the X-axis.
15 pP._xProjectionBound = new Dimension(-1.0f,
  2.0f);

```

4.2. Creating and uploading data sets [T]

Source package:

`t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t2_plot3d.t2`

This tutorial showcases how to upload data sets to *Plot3D*. As already explained, the overall process is very similar to how one can provide data sets for 2D visualization (see the code snippet in Listing 25).

The two obvious differences are: *DataSet.getFor3D()* method should be used instead of its 2D counterpart to establish a proper data set object instance, and data points attributes should consist of at least three attributes mapped into X (index of 0), Y (index of 1), and Z (index of 2) display ranges.

Apart from the above, one should be aware of the problem of size determination when mixing rendering modes. Specifically, OpenGL introduces two rendering options: `GL_POINTS` and `GL_LINES`. They are the most efficient rendering options as they do not involve additional information on the object’s ‘‘volume’’. However, the problem of determining suitable object size arises when having no volume. To resolve this, OpenGL determines the size based on the size of the raster, i.e., a flat 2D object (which may ultimately lead to awkwardly looking renders). The JECMD uses these modes in three cases: a line object is drawn with a *Line.REGULAR* style, marker edges are drawn, or marker style is set to *Marker.POINT_3D*. Suppose the plot involves a data set with other styles (that use other rendering modes). In that case, the problem of size scale incompatibility arises (for styles involving the volume, sizes typically reflect the size in the rendering space 1:1). If so, the user must be aware of it and manually adjust the most suitable size values. Additionally, the legend entry sizes may need to be adjusted (as explained in Listing 25)).

The expected render is depicted in Figure 23. Note that the Z-dimension is directed in a way that negative values point to the observer (out of the screen).

Listing 25: Specifying data sets to be displayed on Plot 3D

```

// The blocks of code below create three
  data sets in a way similar to how data
  sets for plot 2D are created.
// Naturally, data points now consist of
  three attributes. Note that DataSet.
  getFor3D method is used now to

```


Figure 23: Basic example of a 3D plot

```

// create a suitable DataSet object.
ArrayList<IDataSet> dataSets = new
    ArrayList<>(4);
5 {
    // The data sets consists of 5 points.
    // They are to be displayed using red
    // cubes with black edges (marker style
    // with an edge style specified).
    double [][] data = new double [][]
    {
10     {-1.0f, -1.0f, -1.0f},
        {-0.5f, -0.5f, -0.5f},
        {0.0f, 0.0f, 0.0f},
        {0.5f, 0.5f, 0.5f},
        {1.0f, 1.0f, 1.0f}
15     };

    //Important note: sizes typically reflect
    // the size in the rendering space 1:1
    // in the 3D mode
    // Hence, a centrally located cube with a
    // size of 1.0 (100% for 3D rendering)
    // will cover all the drawing area.
    // The exception is when the 3D shape is
    // drawn using GL_LINES or GL_POINTS
    // options. Then, the OpenGL
20 // determines the size based on the
    // raster size. These modes are used in
    // the following situations:
    // - When drawing a marker edge (GL_LINES
    // )
    // - When a line style is specified for a
    // data set and Line.REGULAR style is
    // used (default option; GL_LINES).
    // - When a marker style is specified and

```

```

        a Marker.POINT_3D shape is used (
        GL_POINTS).
    // Consequently, when different styles
    // are mixed, the size scale may seem
    // inconsistent, and preferred size
    // values must be determined manually (
    // this is the case for the three data
    // sets). Note that, however,
    // this may cause glitches in legend
    // rendering as the marker/lines drawn
    // for legend entries have sizes
    // determined relative to one another (
    // hence, if one data set has a size 100
    // larger than the size of
    // another data set, its legend entry will
    // also be 100 times bigger). To resolve
    // this issue, an additional
    // parameter can be passed via marker/
    // line style object: legend size. This
    // size will be used when rendering
    // legend entries instead of the
    // dynamically determined one if provided
    .

    // Edges are drawn in the GL_LINES mode,
    // hence the line size scale differs from
    // the marker size scale
    LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(1.0f, Color.
        BLACK, 0.05f); // bypass legend entry
        size
    MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(0.05f,
        Color.RED, Marker.CUBE_3D, ls);
    dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor3D("DS1", data
        , ms));
}

{
    // 5 data points drawn using a marker
    // with a gradient fill color specified (
    // without edges and line connections)
    double [][] data = new double [][]
    {
40     {-1.0f, 0.25f, 0.25f},
        {-0.5f, 0.25f, 0.25f},
        {0.0f, 0.25f, 0.25f},
        {0.5f, 0.25f, 0.25f},
        {1.0f, 0.25f, 0.25f},
45     };

    // Assuming the style is set to Marker.
    // POINT_3D, the marker size scale will
    // be different.
    MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(0.05f,
        Gradient.getPlasmaGradient(), 0,
        Marker.SPHERE_HIGH_POLY_3D);
    dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor3D("DS2", data
        , ms));
}

{
    // Line determined by 3 points.
    double [][] data = new double [][]
    {
55     {

```

```

    {-1.0f, -1.0f, 1.0f},
    {0.0f, -1.0f, -0.25f},
    {1.0f, 0.5f, -0.5f},
    };
    // The commented line uses a default Line
    .REGULAR shape, which uses a different
    line width scale.
    //LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(0.05f,
    Gradient.getViridisGradient(), 2);
    LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(0.05f,
    Gradient.getViridisGradient(), 2, Line
    .POLY_OCTO);
    dataSets.add(DataSet.getFor3D("DS3", data
    , ls));
}

```

This brief tutorial shows how plot scales can be customized in a similar way to how they can be in *Plot2D*. The most relevant code snippets from this tutorial are presented in Listing 26, while the expected output is depicted in Figure 25. Note that this example is built on the tutorial in Section 4.3.

4.3. Creating a colorbar and using a non-coordinate-dependent gradient [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t2_plot3d.t3

This tutorial can be considered a 3D adaptation of a tutorial presented in Section 3.11 that explained how to depict points whose coordinates are drawn from a Gaussian distribution and color them based on their distance to the plot origin. The expected result is presented in Figure 24. Note that the code extends the right margins (relative size of 0.3) and shrinks the colorbar.

Figure 25: Plot with customized scales

Figure 24: Using gradients and the colorbar

4.4. Using nonlinear scales [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t2_plot3d.t4

Listing 26: Customizing scales

```

// Let's specify some arbitrarily selected
// normalization functions for each
// dimension:
pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[0].
    setNormalizer(new Gamma(2.0f));
pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[1].
    setNormalizer(new Gamma(4.5f));
pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[2].
    setNormalizer(new Gamma(0.5f));
5 pP._pDisplayRangesManager._DR[3].
    setNormalizer(new Gamma(0.75d));

// Axes and grids can be customized in the
// following way:
NumberFormat format = new DecimalFormat();
ITicksDataGetter xTDG = new
    FromDisplayRange(pP.
        _pDisplayRangesManager._DR[0],5, format)
    ;
10 xTDG.setForcedUnnormalizedLocations(new
    float[]{-1.0f, -0.5f, 0.0f, 0.5f, 1.0f})
    ;
ITicksDataGetter yTDG = new
    FromDisplayRange(pP.
        _pDisplayRangesManager._DR[1],5, format)
    ;
yTDG.setForcedUnnormalizedLocations(new
    float[]{-1.0f, -0.5f, 0.0f, 0.5f, 1.0f})
    ;
ITicksDataGetter zTDG = new
    FromDisplayRange(pP.

```

```

    _pDisplayRangesManager._DR[2],5, format)
    ;
zTDG.setForcedUnnormalizedLocations(new
    float []{-1.0f, -0.5f, 0.0f, 0.5f, 1.0f})
    ;
15 ITicksDataGetter cbTDG = new
    FromDisplayRange(pP.
        _pDisplayRangesManager._DR[3],5, format)
    ;
cbTDG.setForcedUnnormalizedLocations(new
    float []{0.0f, 0.2f, 0.4f, 0.6f, 0.8f,
    1.0f});
((DrawingArea3D) plot.
    getComponentsContainer().getDrawingArea
    ()).setGridlinesTicksDataGetters(xTDG,
    yTDG, zTDG);
((DrawingArea3D) plot.
    getComponentsContainer().getDrawingArea
    ()).setTicksDataGetterForXAxes(xTDG);
((DrawingArea3D) plot.
    getComponentsContainer().getDrawingArea
    ()).setTicksDataGetterForYAxes(yTDG);
20 ((DrawingArea3D) plot.
    getComponentsContainer().getDrawingArea
    ()).setTicksDataGetterForZAxes(zTDG);
plot.getComponentsContainer().getColorbar()
    .getAxis().setTicksDataGetter(cbTDG);

```


Figure 26: Overview of available marker styles

- Envelope rendering is not supported by the default painter object used to depict regular data sets in *Plot2D*. Instead, a different painter object must be used.

4.5. Examining marker style configurations [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t1_plot2d.t5

This final tutorial briefly overviews various marker style configurations available in the 3D mode. The source code is straightforward; hence, it is not brought here. The expected render is illustrated in Figure 26. Note that although transparency is available in this mode (a proper flag must be set in plot parameters contained and via data set getter), it is not optimized. Thus, it is not recommended to use it (glitches may appear due to depth-related issues).

5. Convergence plot for 2D visualization [T]

Convergence plots are commonly used to illustrate data that can be represented as a time series (e.g., an algorithm’s performance in subsequent iterations). The visualization module, however, does not introduce a class dedicated to convergence plots per se (e.g., *ConvergencePlot2D*). Instead, a convergence plot can be achieved by suitably parameterizing *Plot2D* and the input data set.

First, the implemented convergence plot functionality allows for the upper and lower deviations from the data series’ y-coordinate values to be provided and rendered using an envelope. This required to make two slight adaptations to how *Plot2D* is operated:

- The display ranges manager has to be adapted to handle deviations from data points’ y-coordinate values.

When it comes to the first, the parameterization for a display range manager for the convergence plot differs from this for *Plot2D*. Although the number of display ranges (and their purpose) is the same, i.e., two: for the X and the Y axes, the attribute-to-display-range mapping is different. Specifically, it is assumed that the input data points for the convergence plot can take one of the two following forms: [X-coordinate, Y-coordinate] or [X-coordinate, Y-coordinate, Y-coordinate + upper deviation, Y-coordinate – lower deviation]. The latter form can be used if deviation-like data accompanies the original (X, Y) data and one wants to visualize it (the convergence plot illustrates an envelope for this purpose). Notably, these two extra attributes should be linked to the Y-axis. Therefore, the mapping for the convergence plot is, by default, set as [0 (X-dimension), 1 (Y-dimension), 1, 1] instead of [0, 1]. Such suitably adjusted parameterization can be obtained by calling: *pP.pDisplayRangesManager = DisplayRangesManager.Params.getForConvergencePlot2D()*. **Important note:** the X-axis is considered a timeline. Therefore, the first attribute values of the input data points should be monotonically increasing.

When it comes to the rendering, a *dataset.DataSet.getForConvergencePlot2D()* static method can be called to retrieve a suitably parameterized data set object that wraps a proper painter (instead of calling *dataset.DataSet.getForPlot2D()*).

5.1. Creating and displaying a convergence plot

Source package:
t1.t10.t1.visualization.module.t3.convergence_plot.2d.t1

This tutorial showcases how to create a convergence plot. It focuses on proper display ranges manager params formularization and data set construction. The most relevant code snippets are in Listing 27, while the expected output is illustrated in Figure 27. The five data sets rendered present various customization options worth acquiring. Unfortunately, the envelope accompanying a data set is not reflected in the legend entry (to be implemented).

Figure 27: Example convergence plot

Listing 27: Creating and displaying a convergence plot

```
pP._pDisplayRangesManager =
    DisplayRangesManager.Params.
    getForConvergencePlot2D();

[...]

// The blow code block instantiates data
// series
ArrayList<IDataSet> dataSets = new
    ArrayList<>();
int iterations = 100;
{
    // The following data set uses the two-
    // element tuple representation (no
    // deviation). It will be depicted
    // using a regular red line (no markers).
    double[][] data = new double[iterations
        ][2];
    for (int i = 0; i < iterations; i++)
    {
```

```
        data[i][0] = i; // X-coordinate
        data[i][1] = 0.25f + 1.0f / Math.pow(i
            + 1, 0.5f); //Y-coordinate
    }
    LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(1.0f, Color.
        RED);
    // DataSet.getForConvergencePlot2D must
    // be used to instantiate a data set to
    // be illustrated in a convergence plot.
    IDataset ds = DataSet.
        getForConvergencePlot2D("CP1", data,
            null, ls, null);
    dataSets.add(ds);
}

{
    // The below data uses the four-tuple
    // representation (deviation is used). It
    // will be depicted using a red
    // line and a transparent reddish
    // envelope.
    double[][] data = new double[iterations
        ][4];
    for (int i = 0; i < iterations; i++)
    {
        data[i][0] = i;
        data[i][1] = 1.0f / (i + 1);
        data[i][2] = data[i][1] + 0.1f;
        data[i][3] = data[i][1] - 0.1f;
    }
    LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(0.2f, Color.
        RED);
    // The envelope color can be provided as
    // the last constructor parameter (
    // transparency is supported).
    IDataset ds = DataSet.
        getForConvergencePlot2D("CP2", data,
            ls,
            new color.Color(1.0f, 0.0f, 0.0f, 0.25f))
            ;
    dataSets.add(ds);
}

{
    // This data will be depicted using an
    // envelope only (no lines or markers).
    double[][] data = new double[iterations
        ][4];
    for (int i = 0; i < iterations; i++)
    {
        data[i][0] = i;
        data[i][1] = 1.5f - (float) i /100.0f;
        data[i][2] = data[i][1] + 0.1f;
        data[i][3] = data[i][1] - 0.1f;
    }
    IDataset ds = DataSet.
        getForConvergencePlot2D("CP3", data, (
            LineStyle) null,
            new color.Color(0.0f, 1.0f, 0.0f, 0.25f))
            ;
    dataSets.add(ds);
}
```

```

55 {
    // This data will use markers (colored
    // using gradients), the line, and the
    // envelope. Note that the input
    // data points are densely spaced,
    // meaning marker rendering may obscure
    // visibility. However, one can adjust
    // the starting data point index (phase)
    // and after how many data points a
    // marker should be rendered (interval).
60 // These can be specified as two marker
    // style fields: ‘_paintEvery’ and ‘_
    // _startPaintingFrom’
    // (see the lines below).
    double [][] data = new double[iterations
    ][4];
    for (int i = 0; i < iterations; i++)
    {
65     data[i][0] = i;
        data[i][1] = 1.75f - (float) i /100.0f;
        data[i][2] = data[i][1] + 0.1f;
        data[i][3] = data[i][1] - 0.1f;
    }
70 MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(2.0f,
    Gradient.getMagmaGradient(), 0, Marker
    .SQUARE);
    LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(0.5f, Color.
    BLUE);
    ms._paintEvery = 5;
    ms._startPaintingFrom = 5;
    IDataset ds = DataSet.
        getForConvergencePlot2D("CP4", data,
        ms, ls,
75 new color.Color(0.0f, 0.0f, 1.0f, 0.25f))
        ;
    dataSets.add(ds);
}
{
    // The data set below demonstrates that
    // the break can be introduced into
    // rendered convergence curves
80 // (in the same way as breaks are
    // introduced into regular lines).
    LinkedList<double [][]> data = new
    LinkedList<>();
    {
        double [][] d = new double[40][4];
        for (int i = 0; i < 40; i++)
        {
85             d[i][0] = i;
                d[i][1] = 2.0f - (float) i /100.0f;
                d[i][2] = d[i][1] + 0.1f;
                d[i][3] = d[i][1] - 0.1f;
            }
        data.add(d);
    }
    data.add(null);
    {
95         double [][] d = new double[40][4];
            int start = 60;
            for (int i = start; i < iterations; i

```

```

        ++)
        {
            d[i - start][0] = i;
            d[i - start][1] = 2.0f - (float)
            i /100.0f;
            d[i - start][2] = d[i - start][1]
            + 0.1f;
            d[i - start][3] = d[i - start][1]
            - 0.1f;
        }
        data.add(d);
    }
}

MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(2.0f,
    Gradient.getRedBlueGradient(), 0,
    Marker.CIRCLE);
ms._paintEvery = 10;
ms._startPaintingFrom = 5;
IDataset ds = DataSet.
    getForConvergencePlot2D("CP5", data,
    ms,
    new color.Color(1.0f, 0.0f, 1.0f, 0.25f))
    ;
dataSets.add(ds);
}

```

5.2. Using nonlinear scales [T]

Source package:

`t1.t10.t1.visualization.module.t3.convergence_plot_2d.t2`

This brief tutorial explains how to use nonlinear scales with convergence plots. No code snippets are brought here since the process is analogous to scale customization in the regular *Plot2D*. The expected convergence plot that uses a logarithmic scale for the Y-axis is depicted in Figure 28.

6. Parallel coordinate plot for 2D visualization

As with the convergence plot, the parallel coordinate plot requires a specially parameterized display ranges params container and uses a different data set constructor. Additionally, a dedicated class *plot.parallelcoordinate.ParallelCoordinatePlot2D* is introduced. The reason for this is to alter the original *Plot2D* component composition and ensure that it aligns with the display ranges manager and dedicated painters matched with uploaded data sets. The most significant alternation is the re-composition of axes. Now, instead of 2 axes, $1 + n$ axes components are maintained. The first one is dedicated to the X-axis, while the remaining n is associated with assumed n dimensions (assumed space dimensionality).

Regarding the display ranges manager parameterization, $n + 1$ display ranges are assumed to be maintained. The first n display ranges correspond to the vertical axes (dimensions), and they can be freely and independently to one another parameterized (e.g., dynamic update flags set to true/false). The last display range is associated with the X-axis and is fixed at the [0,

Figure 28: Plot with nonlinear scales

Figure 29: Example parallel coordinate plot

1] interval (it contrasts the order in which axes are maintained to ensure more natural access to display ranges, i.e., from the index of 0, as they are more frequently being accessed than the axes components). When it comes to the mapping, the array takes the following form $[0, 1, \dots, n - 1]$. Noticeably, no attribute is mapped into the last display range. The reason is that it is explicitly reserved and exploited by the painter dedicated to a parallel coordinate plot (not accessible, e.g., to gradients; this also means that the data x-coordinate values are not meant to be provided – they are calculated automatically). The valid parameterization of the display ranges params container can be obtained via “*getForParallelCoordinatePlot2D*” static methods in *plot.parallelcoordinate.ParallelCoordinatePlot2D.Params* class.

Concerning the input data, each data point will be rendered as a continuous line passing through all parallel vertical axes at valid positions. One point is supposed to be modeled as one row in the *double[][]* matrix provided when instantiating a data set object, and it is supposed to be an *n*-element vector, where the *i*-th attribute corresponds to the *i*-th dimension.

6.1. Creating and displaying a parallel coordinate plot [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.
t4_parallel_coordinate_plot_2d.t1

This tutorial introduces how a parallel coordinate plot can be instantiated and displayed. It employs simple and understandable data. The comments in the provided code snippets in Listing 28 discuss various plot construction aspects. The expected render is depicted in Figure 29.

Listing 28: Creating and displaying a parallel coordinate plot

```
// The below line instantiates a params
// container for the parallel coordinate
// plot. As can be observed,
// the constructor accepts the integer
// representing the space dimensionality.
// This number will reflect
// the number of parallel vertical axes.
ParallelCoordinatePlot2D.Params pP = new
ParallelCoordinatePlot2D.Params(3);

// Use a customized white scheme
pP._scheme = WhiteScheme.getForPCP2D();

[...]

// Each parallel vertical axis can be
// appointed a label. These labels can be
// passed via the below field.
pP._axesTitles = new String[]{"D1", "D2", "
D3"};

[...]

// This plot type uses a suitably adjusted
// display ranges manager. Specifically, it
// is assumed that n + 1 display
// ranges are maintained, where n denotes
// the space dimensionality. The first n
// display ranges correspond to the
// vertical axes (dimensions), and they can
// be freely and independently to one
// another parameterized (e.g.,
// dynamic update flags set to true/false).
// In turn, the last display range is
// associated with the X-axis and is
```

```

20 // fixed at the [0, 1] interval. Regarding
    the mapping, the array takes the
    following form [0,1,...n - 1].
    Noticeably,
// no attribute is mapped into the last
display range. The reason is that it is
explicitly reserved and exploited
// by the painter dedicated to a parallel
coordinate plot (not accessible, e.g.,
to gradients). The valid
// parameterization of the display ranges
params container can be obtained via ‘‘
getForParallelCoordinatePlot2D’’
// static methods.
25 pP._pDisplayRangesManager =
    DisplayRangesManager.Params.
    getForParallelCoordinatePlot2D(3,
Range.getNormalRange(), false);

[...]

30 // Finally, the ParallelCoordinatePlot2D
    object can be instantiated.
ParallelCoordinatePlot2D plot = new
    ParallelCoordinatePlot2D(pP);

[...]

35 ArrayList<IDataSet> dataSets = new
    ArrayList<>();
{
    // The raw data to be illustrated on the
    parallel coordinate plot consists of a
    series of n-dimensional data
    // points (n equals the number of
    attributes). Each data point will be
    rendered as a continuous line passing
    // through all parallel vertical axes at
    valid positions. One point is modeled
    as one row in the double[][]
40 // matrix provided when instantiating a
    data set object, and it is supposed to
    be an n-element vector, where
    // the i-th attribute corresponds to the
    i-th dimension. Note that, in the
    example data below, the line
    // defined as {1.0d, 2.0d, 0.0d} would
    barely be visible if the display
    ranges were fixed at [0, 1] intervals
    // (i.e., the dynamic update flag was set
    to false).
    double[][] data = new double[][]{{0.0d,
        0.0d, 1.0d}, {1.0d, 2.0d, 0.0d}, {0.5d
        , 0.5d, -0.5d}};
45 // Notably, markers/lines can be colored
    using a gradient linked to one of the
    1-n display ranges
    // (the last display range is not
    accessible).
    LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(2, Gradient.
        getPlasmaGradient(), 2);
    LineStyle mes = new LineStyle(1, Gradient

```

```

        .getBlueRedGradient(), 2);
    MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(5,
    Gradient.getViridisGradient(), 0,
    Marker.SQUARE, mes);
50 // A data set object that is suitably
    parameterized for the parallel
    coordinate plot can be obtained by
    // using ‘‘getForParallelCoordinatePlot2D
    ’’ static factory-like methods.
    dataSets.add(DataSet.
        getForParallelCoordinatePlot2D("DS1",
        3, data, ms, ls));
}

```

6.2. Providing multiple data sets [T]

Source package:
t1-t10.t1-visualization-module.
t4-parallel-coordinate-plot-2d.t2

The following tutorial explains and showcases that the parallel coordinate plot can be fed with multiple data sets in a way similar to how data sets are provided to *Plot2D*. Since the source code is straightforward, no code snippet is brought here. The expected render of a parallel coordinate plot with two data sets is illustrated in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Parallel coordinate plot with multiple data sets

6.3. Customizing the plot [T]

Source package:
t1-t10.t1-visualization-module.
t4-parallel-coordinate-plot-2d.t3

This next tutorial discusses various ways the parallel coordinate plot can be customized. It includes, e.g., disabling rendering of those tick labels that would obscure the plot readability, adding a colorbar, or changing the number format used. It is worth noticing that the example in the given source code treats the space dimensionality as a variable (parameter), while the data to be visualized is generated randomly using a Gaussian distribution. This way, the user may inspect various outcomes. The most relevant code snippets from this tutorial can be found in Listing 29, while the final render for the 5-dimensional case is depicted in Figure 31.

Listing 29: Customizing a parallel coordinate plot

```

// The below field is used to parameterize
// the number of dimensions
int dims = 5;

[...]

// Define the vertical axes' labels:
pP._axesTitles = ParallelCoordinatePlot2D.
  getAxesTitlesAsSequence("D", dims);

[...]

pP._pDisplayRangesManager =
  DisplayRangesManager.Params.
  getForParallelCoordinatePlot2D(dims,
  Range.getNormalRange(), true);

[...]

// Add a colorbar that is linked to the
// first dimension (index of 0).
pP._colorbar = new Colorbar(Gradient.
  getPlasmaGradient(), "COLORBAR", new
  FromDisplayRange(pP.
  _pDisplayRangesManager._DR[0], 10));

// This flag can be set to true to turn off
// those ticks that would obscure plot
// readability.
pP._disableOverlappingTicks = true;

ParallelCoordinatePlot2D plot = new
  ParallelCoordinatePlot2D(pP);

[...]

{
  // Let's create 2000 data points
  // artificially.
  int lines = 2000;

  double [][] data = new double [lines][dims
  ];
  IRandom R = new MersenneTwister64(1);

  // The attribute values will be drawn
  // from the Gaussian distribution.
  // The mean is drawn randomly (for each
  attribute), while the std is defined
  // as (1 - mean)^2
  double [] means = new double [dims];
  double [] std = new double [dims];
  for (int i = 0; i < dims; i++)
  {
    means[i] = R.nextDouble();
    std[i] = Math.pow(1.0d - means[i], 2.0d
    );
  }

  // Create data points here.
  for (int i = 0; i < lines; i++)
    for (int j = 0; j < dims; j++)
      data[i][j] = means[j] + R.
        nextGaussian() * std[j];

  // Render the data points using a
  // gradient color determined based on the
  // first attribute value.
  LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(0.25f,
    Gradient.getPlasmaGradient(), 0);
  IDataset ds = DataSet.
    getForParallelCoordinatePlot2D("DS 1",
    dims, data, null, ls);
  plot.getModel().setDataSet(ds, true);
}

// The below lines specify a decimal number
// formatter to all vertical axes and the
// colorbar axis. Note that the
// axes returned by the getAxes() method
// are stored as follows: the first (zero
// index) axis is linked to the
// X-axis, while the remaining n axes
// represent the vertical ones. Hence, the
// '1 + i' index is used in the
// loop below to access the vertical axes.
NumberFormat numberFormat = new
  DecimalFormat();
for (int i = 0; i < dims; i++) plot.
  getComponentsContainer().getAxes()[1 +
  i].getTicksDataGetter().setNumberFormat(
  numberFormat);
plot.getComponentsContainer().getColorbar()
  .getAxis().getTicksDataGetter().
  setNumberFormat(numberFormat);

```

6.4. Using custom display ranges [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.
t4_parallel_coordinate_plot_2d.t4

This tutorial shows how to employ a custom display range to color the data set based on a custom attribute. The parallel coordinate plot allows the use of custom display ranges, but they must be positioned explicitly between the first M (M is the number of objectives) display ranges associated with the paral-

Figure 31: Customized parallel coordinate plot

Figure 32: Parallel coordinate plot with custom display range associated with the gradient

lel coordinate lines and the last display range reserved for the X-axis.

This tutorial extends the one introduced in Section 6.3. Here, the assumed scenario is that one wishes to color each data point based on the sum of its attribute values. For this reason, the original M -element data points are extended by one attribute, whose value is defined as a sum of the values of previous ones. Also, an additional (custom) display range is put between the first M display ranges and the last one (reserved for the X-axis). Furthermore, colorbar and line-style gradient bindings are mapped into the custom display range. Since the modifications applied to the tutorial's source code in Section 6.3 are straightforward, they are not brought here. Figure 32 depicts the expected render.

7. Heatmap for 2D visualization

Heatmap is one of the most fundamental visualization tools. This section discusses its 2D implementation in JECDM. Similarly to the previously introduced specialized plots, this implementation is founded on general components and directly extends the `Plot2D` class. Hence, its use is similar to that of this parent plot.

7.1. Creating and displaying a plot [T]

```
Source package:
t1.t10.t1.visualization.module.t5.heatmap.2d.t1
```

Code snippets in Listing 30 showcase how a heatmap 2D can be instantiated. First, it is essential to understand that the heatmap

is implemented as an additional layer to the regular plot (explicitly rendered over the plot's drawing area). Hence, the display ranges assumed for the regular plot explicitly determine the part of the data space to be discretized. The discretization is done for each dimension, and the discretization level can be provided via the Heatmap2D params container (*xDiv* and *yDiv* integers). They determine how many slices each display bound will be divided into. The Cartesian product of these slices are called boxes/buckets in this framework.

The provided listing also emphasizes that each bucket contains a value (double). The visualization tool will color the buckets using a gradient, assuming that the colors will be determined based on the buckets' normalized values. For this reason, the two additional parameters must be specified via the params container: the display range associated with bucket values and a gradient. **Important note:** providing custom display manager params should be avoided in the current version of JECDM. The reason is that the heatmap object will, during initialization, create a display manager by jointly considering the provided params container and the heatmap display range. Therefore, even though the "getFor2D" method is used for 2D visualization, the heatmap object will add the third display range associated with the heatmap. Consequently, conflicts may occur when providing a custom (non-standard) params container.

Finally, the input data format is discussed. It is a simple *double[][]* matrix. It is assumed that the matrix cells correspond 1:1 with the discretized bucket coordinates. The first dimension (index) is linked to the Y-dimension, while the second with X. Additionally, the *matrix[0]* row will be rendered at the bottom, while the *matrix[index of the last row]* will be rendered at the top. Similarly, the first column is associated with the left side of the plot, while the last column with the right.

Overall, this tutorial concerns a very simple heatmap (4 columns x 3 rows) to acquaint the reader with the heatmap most conveniently. The expected heatmap generated by the tutorial's source code is illustrated in Figure 33.

Listing 30: Creating and displaying heatmap 2D

```
// First, a params container for the
// heatmap must be instantiated.
Heatmap2D.Params pP = new Heatmap2D.Params
    ();

// The two below param fields are essential
// as they can be used to specify a
// discretization level for each
// dimension. In the example below, the X-
// dimension will be divided three times,
// while the Y-dimension will be four.
pP._xDiv = 3;
pP._yDiv = 4;

pP._xAxisTitle = "X - dimension";
pP._yAxisTitle = "Y - dimension";

// Heatmap 2D uses regular parameterization
// of display ranges in the params
// container as it is assumed that the
```


Figure 33: Example heatmap 2D

```
// discretization is done on a specified
// part of 2D plane (as done when using
// Plot2D). Note that Heatmap2D does
// not perform the heatmap rendering
// explicitly on the drawing area
// maintained by the parent Plot2D class.
// Instead, it involves an additional layer
// that is put explicitly on the main
// drawing area to handle rendering.
pP._pDisplayRangesManager =
    DisplayRangesManager.Params.getFor2D(
        Range.getNormalRange(), Range.
        getNormalRange());

// However, an additional display range
// explicitly associated with the buckets'
// values must be specified
// (bucket or box = discretization product)
// . The configuration below states that
// the range is initially unknown
// but will be determined dynamically.
pP._heatmapDisplayRange = new
    DisplayRangesManager.DisplayRange(null,
    true);

// Additionally, a gradient used to color
// the buckets (and associated with the
// above display range) must be specified.
pP._gradient = Gradient.getViridisGradient
    ();

// The following line constructs the
// Heatmap2D object.
Heatmap2D plot = new Heatmap2D(pP);

[...]
```

```

30 // At the lowest level, the input data for
    // Heatmap2D is a 2D double matrix
    // storing values associated with
    // buckets. It is assumed by default that
    // the first dimension of the matrix (row)
    // is linked to bucket's
    // Y-coordinate (from bottom to top), while
    // the column number reflects the X-
    // coordinate (from left to right).
    // For instance, consider the data below.
    // The data[0][0] = 2.0f value will be
    // reflected at the left-bottom corner
35 // of the plot, while data[3][2] = 1.0f
    // value at the right-bottom.
    double [][] data = new double [][]
    {
        {2.0f, 2.0f, 3.0f},
        {2.0f, 3.0f, 2.0f},
40 {2.0f, 5.0f, 2.0f},
        {1.0f, 2.0f, 1.0f},
    };

    // The model object linked to Heatmap2D (
    // plot.getModel()) provides new methods
    // for uploading heatmap data.
45 // The line below contains the most basic
    // way for data upload.
    plot.getModel().setDataAndPerformProcessing
        (data);

```


Figure 34: Example heatmap 2D with customized axes

7.2. Customizing the plot [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t5_heatmap_2d.t2

This brief tutorial concerns the basic customization of heatmap axes. Specifically, it shows how one can reposition their ticks to be located near the centers of heatmap columns/rows. Also, a way of specifying custom tick labels is shown. Finally, it shows how to turn on grid line rendering. Overall, this tutorial may be helpful when parameterizing a heatmap with low number of columns and rows. The code snippets are provided in Listing 31, while the final render is in Figure 34.

Listing 31: Creating and customizing heatmap 2D

```

// The below line will make the main grid
// lines renderable, while the following
// two lines will enforce the
// grid lines to align with the buckets'
// boundaries.
pP._drawMainGridlines = true;
pP._horizontalGridLinesWithBoxTicks = true;
5 pP._verticalGridLinesWithBoxTicks = true;

// The two lines below will enforce the
// axes' ticks to be located at the centers
// of columns/rows that emerge
// from the buckets/boxes.
pP._yAxisWithBoxTicks = true;

```

```

10 pP._xAxisWithBoxTicks = true;

[... ]

// The two lines below provide custom
// labels for axes' ticks (that point to
// columns/rows).
15 plot.getComponentsContainer().getAxes()[0].
    getTicksDataGetter().
    setPredefinedTickLabels(new String[]{"
        COL 0", "COL 1", "COL 2"});
plot.getComponentsContainer().getAxes()[1].
    getTicksDataGetter().
    setPredefinedTickLabels(new String[]{"
        ROW 0", "ROW 1", "ROW 2", "ROW3"});

```

7.3. Using nonlinear scales and displaying regular data sets [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t5_heatmap_2d.t3

This tutorial can be considered a continuation of the tutorial introduced in Section 7.2. It reveals how nonlinearity can be introduced in bucket positioning. As with adjusting regular scales, the introduction of nonlinearity can be achieved by providing dedicated normalizers. They can be supplied by the heatmap params container. The tutorial also shows that a heatmap 2D can display the “regular” data sets, i.e. as if it was *Plot2D*. The regular data sets are projected using the regular display ranges, i.e., those maintained by the display ranges manager.

This tutorial’s most relevant code snippets are listed in Listing 32, while the final plot is in Figure 35.

Figure 35: Example heatmap 2D with nonlinear scales and a regular data set

Listing 32: Using nonlinear scales

```
// The bucket coordinates are obtained
// using a separate normalizer (normalizer
// independent of the one set in the
// associated display range). The two lines
// below show how to specify the
// normalizer for bucket coordinates.
pP._xBucketCoordsNormalizer = new Gamma(0.5
f);
pP._yBucketCoordsNormalizer = new Gamma(2.0
f);
[...]

// A heatmap used to color the boxes (
// buckets) can also employ a non-linear
// scale (see the line below).
pP._heatmapDisplayRange.setNormalizer(new
Gamma(0.5f));
[...]

// Let's draw the legend.
pP._drawLegend = true;
[...]

// Also, let's draw the colorbar. Notice
// that the ticks data getter now points
// to pP._heatmapDisplayRange.
pP._colorbar = new Colorbar(pP._gradient, "
Value", new FromDisplayRange(pP.
_heartbeatDisplayRange, 5));
pP._scheme = new WhiteScheme();
pP._scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
MARGIN_RIGHT_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER,
```

```
0.25f);

//The ticks can be adjusted similarly to
//how it is done in Plot2D.
plot.getComponentsContainer().getColorbar()
.getAxis().getTicksDataGetter().
setNumberFormat(new DecimalFormat());
25 plot.getComponentsContainer().getColorbar()
.getAxis().getTicksDataGetter().
setForcedUnnormalizedLocations(
new float[]{1.0f, 2.0f, 3.0f, 4.0f, 5.0f});

// Extra: a heatmap is just an additional
// layer rendered over the drawing area of
// Plot2D, and the functionality
// of this regular plot is not hidden.
// Therefore, one can still display "
// standard" data sets (see the below code
// block).
30 {
double [][] plot2D_data = new double [][]
{
{0.0f, 0.0f},
{0.5f, 0.5f},
35 {1.0f, 1.0f}
};
MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(5.0f,
Color.RED, Marker.CIRCLE);
LineStyle ls = new LineStyle(1.0f, Color.
BLACK);
IDataSet ds = DataSet.getFor2D("Plot 2D
data set", plot2D_data, ms, ls);
plot.getModel().setDataSet(ds);
}
40
```

7.4. Using a heatmap to illustrate a density function [T]

Source package:

`t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t5_heatmap_2d.t4`

The following tutorial uses random data points generated from the Gaussian distribution as the primary input. It shows how these points can be projected into buckets (space discretization) and displayed. Overall, the resulting heatmap can be interpreted – to some extent – as a visualization of a 2D probability density function (probability of sampling a data point; the data should be, in fact, linearly rescaled to account for probability, i.e., bucket values should be divided by their sum). The most relevant code snippets from this tutorial are presented in Listing 33, while the final render can be found in Figure 36.

Listing 33: Displaying Gaussian distribution

```
// Let's now consider a parametric number
// of x/y divisions:
int xDiv = 100;
int yDiv = 100;

// Additionally, let the display range be
// parametric.
Range RX = new Range(1.5f, 2.5f);
```


Figure 36: Heatmap 2D illustrating a Gaussian distribution

```

Range RY = new Range(-0.5f, 0.5f);

// A double 2D matrix is first instantiated
// (note that the first dimension is
// linked to the Y-axis, while the
// latter is to X).
double[][] data = new double[yDiv][xDiv];

// The object constructed below is a
// supportive tool that allows retrieving
// bucket coordinates (indices, i.e.,
// in the discretized space) given the
// input x and y coordinates (in the
// original space). The object constructor
// requires the following parameters: the
// number of dimensions and divisions per
// each dimension (in the "normal"
// order, i.e., X, Y,...), the bounds (
// Range) associated with each dimension (
// in the normal order),
// and an auxiliary object for retrieving
// the discretized indices from the double
// input (here, a simple linear
// interpolation with thresholding is used)
BucketCoordsTransform B = new
    BucketCoordsTransform(2, new int[]{xDiv,
    yDiv},
    new Range[]{RX, RY}, new
    LinearlyThresholded());

// Create the RNG.
IRandom R = new MersenneTwister64(0);

// The below variable represents the
// number of input data points to sample.
int trials = 100000;

```

```

// Standard deviation of the Gaussian
// distribution
float std = 0.25f;

// This loop generates the input points (X
// and Y coordinates) and projects them
// onto buckets.
for (int i = 0; i < trials; i++)
{
    // Draw X and Y coordinates. Note the
    // mean of the Gaussian distribution is
    // centered near the left-bottom
    // part of the coordinate space (25% of
    // X and 25% of Y).
    float x = (float) (RX.getLeft() + RX.
        getInterval() * 0.25f + R.
        nextGaussian() * std);
    float y = (float) (RY.getLeft() + RY.
        getInterval() * 0.25f + R.
        nextGaussian() * std);

    // The below line constructs the
    // coordinates of a bucket (discretized
    // space) that encapsulates the X and
    // Y
    // coordinates (note that the buckets'
    // intervals are left-side closed and
    // right-side open). If the point
    // falls outside the display ranges,
    // the method returns null.
    int[] c = B.getBucketCoords(new double
        []{x, y});

    // The returned indices are returned in
    // the [X, Y] order. They can be used
    // to increment the proper data
    // entry (note that the heatmap assumes
    // [Y, X] order).
    if (c != null) data[c[1]][c[0]]++;
}

// Set the heatmap data.
plot.getModel().setDataAndPerformProcessing
    (data);

```

7.5. Data presorting and interval-based filtering [T]

Source package:

`t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t5_heatmap_2d.t5`

This tutorial highlights that the input heatmap data can be pre-sorted before uploading. If so, the data will be kept in the form of two sorted arrays, where the elements of the first are bucket coordinates (indices; in the discretized space), while the latter consists of bucket values. The elements of both arrays correspond 1:1 to one another and are sorted in ascending order of values.

The rationale for data presorting is to allow efficient data filtering based on filter-like intervals. The user may specify an interval for bucket values that are supposed to be rendered (buck-

ets whose values do not fall into the interval are skipped). If the heatmap runs in the not-sorted mode, the plot will examine all the buckets before rendering, accepting (or skipping) those that fall (or do not) into the interval. However, if the data is presorted, the visualization tool will quickly (i.e., using the binary search) determine the suitable left and right index bounds for the array elements whose corresponding buckets fall into the desired intervals. Such an approach will often boost filtering efficiency. It is especially true for the 3D mode, where presorting will allow skipping to-GPU transfers (because OpenGL rendering methods allow the rendering of selected parts of the already uploaded buffers).

The interval filter can be supplied in two ways: as it was specified in the normalized or the original space, which is self-explanatory. Regarding the first, it should be a subinterval of [0, 1], and the decision upon whether a bucket should be rendered or not will be based on inspecting its normalized value (i.e., in the 0-1 range). The second assumes that the interval (and the inspected value data) will be specified in the original data space. This tutorial provides four example cases of using the filtering intervals. Their implementations are given in the source code, and their snippets are given in Listing 34. The resulting final renders are depicted in Figures 37- 40.

Side note: the efficient interval filtering (i.e., with presorting) was implemented mainly for the IVEMO-HM [1] tool that visualizes a comprehensive performance of evolutionary methods for multi-objective optimization. An example screenshot if this tool is illustrated in Figure 41.

Figure 37: Example heatmap 2D with interval filtering (case 1, accepts normalized values that fall into [0.0, 0.5] interval)

Listing 34: Data presorting and interval-based filtering

```

int trials = 100000;
float std = 0.25f;

for (int i = 0; i < trials; i++)
{

```

10

Figure 38: Example heatmap 2D with interval filtering (case 2, accepts normalized values that fall into [0.5, 1.0] interval)

Figure 39: Example heatmap 2D with interval filtering (case 3, accepts values that fall into [0.0, 10.0] interval)

```

float x = (float) (RX.getLeft() + RX.
    getInterval() * 0.25f + R.nextGaussian
        () * std);
float y = (float) (RY.getLeft() + RY.
    getInterval() * 0.25f + R.nextGaussian
        () * std);
int[] c = B.getBucketCoords(new double[] {
    x, y});
if (c != null) data[c[1]][c[0]]++;
}

// The "plot.getModel().
// setDataAndPerformProcessing(data);"
// method explicitly passes the processing
// to another
// public method "plot.getModel().

```


Figure 40: Example heatmap 2D with interval filtering (case 4, accepts values that fall into [10.1, 1000000.0] interval)

Figure 41: A screenshot of the IVEMO-HM tool (2D case)

```

setDataAndPerformProcessing(int [][]
data, boolean sort)", with the "sort"
// flag set to false. When this flag is
// true, the input buckets' relevant data (
// coordinates + values) is wrapped
// by auxiliary classes Coords and
// SortedValues and sorted in the ascending
// order of stored values. The reason
// for such a presorting is to boost
// filtering efficiency (at the cost of
// prolonged data preparation time).
// Specifically, Heatmap2D (and 3D) allows

```

```

for the provision of value filters (
intervals that specify which
// buckets should be displayed and which
// should not). If the input data is not
// presorted, all the buckets will
// be inspected to determine whether they
// should be displayed when creating a plot
// render. However, if the
// buckets are presorted, the left and
// right bounds for array indices are
// quickly determined using the binary
// search. These indices specify the subset
// of buckets whose values fall into the
// specified interval and, thus,
// should be rendered. This way of
// processing significantly reduces the
// computational complexity of filtering,
// especially for the 3D mode, where the
// minimization of to-GPU transfers is
// demanded. When the data is presorted,
// no such transfer is required as the
// OpenGL library allows for the selection
// of a subset of a preloaded buffer
// to be rendered (which is implemented in
// this framework).

```

```

// The presorting can be executed on one's
// own. It may be convenient when, e.g.,
// implementing an application
// that makes use of data stored on the
// disc. If so, it is recommended to assume
// a data format in which the bucket
// data is presented in the file. This way,
// no additional sorting would be required
// during runtime. Such sorted
// data can be provided via the "public
// void setDataAndPerformProcessing(Coords
// [] sortedCoords, double[]
// sortedValues)" method, where the first
// array specifies the coordinates (sorted
// according to values), while
// the second represents the sorted values)
// (the elements in both arrays are
// assumed to be connected).

```

```

// The below three lines introduce an
// auxiliary tool, "HeatmapDataProcessor,"
// that can construct sorted
// bucket-related data from the input raw
// data matrix. The fourth line shows how
// to supply the heatmap with
// the presorted data.
HeatmapDataProcessor hdp = new
HeatmapDataProcessor();
Coords[] SC = hdp.getCoords2D(xDiv, yDiv,
data);
HeatmapDataProcessor.SortedValues SV = hdp.
getSortedValues(SC, 2);
plot.getModel().setDataAndPerformProcessing
(SC, SV._sortedValues);
// Note that you can use the below line if

```

```

    you do not want to execute the sorting
    on your own:
//plot.getModel().
    setDataAndPerformProcessing(data, true);
45 // Heatmap introduces two filtering options
    (that can be employed jointly):
    interval-based and masked-based.
// This tutorial introduces the first.
    Consider the following four cases.

// Case 1: First, a value filter can be
    specified in the normalized space, i.e.,
    [0-1]. The left and right bounds
// provided via the following method will
    select an interval for buckets'
    normalized values accepted for rendering
50 // (both sides closed). That is, if a
    bucket's normalized value does not fall
    into this interval, it will not be
// rendered. The below line sets the
    normalized filtering interval to [0.0;
    0.5].
plot.getModel().
    setValueFilterInTheNormalizedSpace(0.0f,
    0.5f);

// Case 2: the normalized interval is set
    to [0.5; 1.0].
55 //plot.getModel().
    setValueFilterInTheNormalizedSpace(0.5f,
    1.0f);

// Case 3: The filtering interval can also
    be specified in the original data space.
    The line below specifies that
// the buckets whose original values (
    provided in data[[]]) are in the given
    range of [0.0; 10.0f] will be rendered.
//plot.getModel().setValueFilter(new Range
    (0.0f, 10.0f));
60

// Case 4: As in case 3, but the interval
    is set to [10.0; 1000000.0].
// plot.getModel().setValueFilter(new Range
    (10.0f, 1000000.0f));

```

7.6. Mask-based filtering [T]

This brief tutorial introduces mask-based filtering. Specifically, an additional boolean matrix of the same dimensionality and size as the input raw data can be provided. The buckets (data elements) and matrix elements are assumed to correspond 1:1. The default flags (i.e., false) indicate that the corresponding bucket should be rendered. At the same time, the value of true will turn off the rendering of a bucket. Not that mask-based filtering does not involve any additional efficiency mechanisms (in contrast to interval filtering).

The example provided can be considered a continuation of the tutorial introduced in Section 7.5. Apart from using interval filtering ([0.25; 1.0], in the normalized space), a mask is used

to filter out the left half of the heatmap. The most relevant code snippets from this tutorial are given in Listing 35, while the expected render can be found in Figure 42.

Figure 42: Heatmap 2D with mask-based filtering

Listing 35: Using mask-based filtering

```

// Let's assume that we want to prohibit
    the rendering of the left half of the
    heatmap. First,
// we need to create a mask matrix (as with
    data, Y dimension goes first, then X):
boolean [][] mask = new boolean[yDiv][xDiv
    ];
5 [...]

int trials = 100000;
float std = 0.25f;

10 for (int i = 0; i < trials; i++)
{
    float x = (float) (RX.getLeft() + RX.
        getInterval() / 2.0f + R.nextGaussian
        () * std);
    float y = (float) (RY.getLeft() + RY.
        getInterval() / 2.0f + R.nextGaussian
        () * std);
    int[] c = B.getBucketCoords(new double[] {
        x, y});
    if (c != null)
    {
        data[c[1]][c[0]]++;
        // The default false value of the mask
        // matrix indicates that the associated
        // bucket is renderable. The
        // below line will set the flag to true
        // (prohibit rendering) if the bucket
        // is placed on the left half
        // of the heatmap.

```

```

    if (c[0] < (float) xDiv / 2) mask[c
        [1]][c[0]] = true;
    }
}
[...]
```

25

```

// The mask can be provided using the below
// line.
plot.getModel().setMask(mask);
30
//Additionally, let's use a value filter (
// normalized):
plot.getModel().
    setValueFilterInTheNormalizedSpace(0.25f
    , 1.0f);
```

8. Heatmap for 3D visualization

The initial release of JECDM provides a heatmap for 3D visualization. Its use is almost identical to that of a heatmap in 2D, so it is straightforward. For this reason, this section introduces tutorials that directly correspond to those in Section 7 for convenience. At the same time, the descriptions provided here are shortened to a bare minimum. There are, however, a few differences between these two sections:

- The differences naturally are related to the greater dimensionality of the space. Thus, e.g., the number of divisions for the Z-dimension must be specified (`_zDiv`), `DisplayRangesManager.Params.getFor3D()` method is recommended to create an initial params container for the display ranges manager, or the raw data should be three-dimensional (the dimensions are ordered from Z to X).
- `Heatmap3D` can also be used to display regular data. However, the tutorials do not cover this aspect, as a regular data set would be barely visible in a 3D heatmap projected on a 2D render. Nonetheless, providing regular data sets is the same as when using `Heatmap2D`.
- `Heatmap3D` introduces bucket styles (very plain ones). These are covered in Section 8.7.

8.1. Creating and displaying a plot [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t6_heatmap_3d.t1

Figure 43 illustrates the final plot generated by the tutorial's source code.

8.2. Customizing the plot [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t6_heatmap_3d.t2

Figure 44 illustrates the final plot generated by the tutorial's source code.

Figure 43: Example heatmap 3D

Figure 44: Example heatmap 3D with customized axes

8.3. Using nonlinear scales [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t6_heatmap_3d.t3

Figure 45 illustrates the final plot generated by the tutorial's source code.

8.4. Using a heatmap to illustrate a density function [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1_visualization_module.t6_heatmap_3d.t4

Figure 45: Example heatmap 3D with nonlinear scales

Figure 47: Example heatmap 3D with interval filtering (case 1, accepts normalized values that fall into [0.0, 0.5] interval)

Figure 46 illustrates the final plot generated by the tutorial's source code. **Side note:** Obviously, the density function per se cannot be observed as this is a 3D plot (the highest density is in the center, apart from the panes' centers, where the highest densities are visible). Nevertheless, the "core" will be revealed in later sections, where the filtration is introduced.

Figure 46: Heatmap 3D illustrating a Gaussian distribution

Figure 48: Example heatmap 3D with interval filtering (case 2, accepts normalized values that fall into [0.5, 1.0] interval)

8.5. Data presorting and interval-based filtering [T]

Source package:
`t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t6_heatmap_3d.t5`

This section uses four similar cases of using an interval filter (similar to those introduced in Section 7.5). The final renders are illustrated in Figures 47-50. Note that for those cases that filter out higher densities, the outcome may seem unchanged (Figure 47 and 49). The reason is that, for these settings, only the middle of the heatmap is filtered out (therefore, it is not visible from the outside observer).

Finally, as with Section 7.5, Figure 51 illustrates an example screenshot of the IVEMO-HM tool [1] run in the 3D mode.

Figure 49: Example heatmap 3D with interval filtering (case 3, accepts values that fall into [0.0, 10.0] interval)

Figure 50: Example heatmap 3D with interval filtering (case 4, accepts values that fall into [10.1, 1000000.0] interval)

Figure 52: Heatmap 2D with mask-based filtering

Figure 51: A screenshot of the IVEMO-HM tool (3D case)

This tutorial shows how to set a bucket style for Heatmap 3D. Specifically, it provides five cases (the relevant code snippet can be found in Listing 36):

1. Default (buckets are rendered as rectangular cuboids; edges are not drawn; example render is already illustrated in Figure 47).
2. Buckets are rendered using GL_POINTS mode. It is the most computationally efficient rendering option but also provides the least readable outcomes (the point size is determined based on the size of the final 2D render). See the expected final render in Figure 53.
3. Buckets are not filled; only edges are drawn (red-blue gradient based on X-axis value); see Figure 54.
4. Buckets are not filled; only edges are drawn (red-blue gradient; color is determined based on the bucket value); see Figure 55. As already explained in Section 7, the display range associated with the heatmap is appended to the regular display ranges during initialization. Hence, it is accessible via the index of 3 (as done in this example).
5. Buckets are filled and the edges are drawn (black color); see Figure 56.

8.6. Mask-based filtering [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t6_heatmap_3d.t6

Figure 52 illustrates the final plot generated by the tutorial's source code.

8.7. Bucket style customization [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t6_heatmap_3d.t7

Listing 36: Using different bucket styles

```
// Bucket style configurations.
// Case 1: Default; buckets are rendered as
// rectangular cuboids; edges are not
// drawn
pP._bucketStyle = BucketStyle.getDefault();
// Case 2: Buckets are rendered using
// GL_POINTS mode.
5 //pP._bucketStyle = BucketStyle.
// getGlPointsStyle(1.0f);
// Case 3: Buckets are not filled; only
// edges are drawn (red-blue gradient based
// on X-axis value);
//pP._bucketStyle = BucketStyle.
// getOnlyEdgesStyle(new LineStyle(0.1f,
// Gradient.getViridisGradient(), 0));
```


Figure 53: Case 2: Buckets are rendered using GL_POINTS mode.

Figure 56: Buckets are filled and the edges are drawn (black color).

Figure 54: Case 3: Buckets are not filled; only edges are drawn (red-blue gradient; color is determined based on X-axis value).

Figure 55: Case 4: Buckets are not filled; only edges are drawn (red-blue gradient; color is determined based on the bucket value).

```
// Case 4: Buckets are not filled; only
edges are drawn (red-blue gradient;
```

```
color is determined based on X-axis
value);
//pP._bucketStyle = BucketStyle.
getOnlyEdgesStyle(new LineStyle(0.1f,
Gradient.getViridisGradient(), 3));
10 // Case 5: Buckets are filled; edges are
drawn (black color);
//pP._bucketStyle = BucketStyle.
getFillAndEdges(new LineStyle(0.1f,
Color.BLACK));
```

9. Customizing the top-level Swing-based components

This tutorial shows how the panel/frame components can be customized, focusing on redefining their incorporated elements and the layout. As discussed in Section 2.5, there are four such components: plot (extensions of *plot.AbstractPlot*), plot wrapper (extensions of *plotwrapper.AbstractPlotWrapper*), plots wrapper (extensions of *plotswrapper.AbstractPlotsWrapper*), and the frame. The first three classes extend the *JPanel* and play the role of major component containers. In turn, the *Frame* class extends *JFrame* and is a displayable object. It is recommended that its potential extensions only be limited to window-related functionalities (the plots wrapper handles top-level plot-related logic). Similarly, one should avoid extending the plot component when designing a GUI. Instead, plot wrapper and plots wrapper should be targeted when customizing the application.

The following tutorials focus on extending the abovementioned plot wrapper (wraps the plot) and plot wrappers (wraps the plot wrappers). They are based on a simple yet general scenario where one wishes to add an extra button to these wrappers. The button logic, however, is not defined (this falls strictly into the scope of Java Swing; hence, it is not discussed here).

9.1. Creating a custom plot wrapper [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t7_top_level_components.t1
 and **shared**

Assume that the goal is to implement a visualization window that is depicted in Figure 57, where the button at the bottom is a member of a plot wrapper (hence, there is an implicit button-plot association). One could try performing adequate modifications on the obtained plot wrapper instance since it is an extension of *JPanel*. However, instead of resolving this problem in this manual and hard-coded way, creating a new wrapper that extends the general abstract class is recommended. Fortunately, the overall design of the abstract class supports implementing custom functionalities.

Figure 57: A window with a customized plot wrapper

Consider the code snippets extracted from *plotwrapper.AbstractPlotWrapper* provided in Listing 37. As with most of the customizable objects in JECM, the parameterization of this class is done via the params container (inner class). When extending such a component, it is recommended that a new params container be implemented for the class extension (the container should extend the parent's container). This way, a hierarchical parameterization path can be implemented (ensuring this way, e.g., generalization, reusability, minimizing code redundancy, etc). Notably, the params container of the abstract class is used to capture the plot object.

Consider next the protected constructor. It accepts the params container and calls three “instantiate” methods: model and controller, GUI, and the layout (in the given order). First, the plot and the wrappers are implemented in the model-view-controller style. It is assumed that the model and the controller are instantiated during the view initialization (*JPanel*). Second, these methods may execute further delegations (each time passing the params container). The delegates are often protected methods that can be overwritten in customized extensions (it is a commonly used pattern in this framework). For instance, consider the *instantiateModelAndController(Params p)* method. If

further delegates the creation of model and controller to *getModelInstance(Params p)* and *getControllerInstance(Params p)* methods, responsible for creating actual object instances. By default, the abstract plot wrapper creates a basic model and controller, uses no GUI (empty method), and uses a basic layout that fills the area with the wrapped plot.

Listing 37: AbstractPlotWrapper class

```

/**
 * Params container.
 */
public static class Params
{
    /**
     * Plot to be displayed.
     */
    public AbstractPlot _plot;

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param plot plot to be displayed
     */
    public Params(AbstractPlot plot)
    {
        _plot = plot;
    }
}

[...]

/**
 * Parameterized constructor.
 *
 * @param p params container
 */
protected AbstractPlotWrapper(Params p)
{
    instantiateModelAndController(p);
    instantiateGUI(p);
    instantiateLayout(p);
}

/**
 * Instantiates the model and the
 * controller.
 *
 * @param p params container
 */
protected void
    instantiateModelAndController(Params p)
{
    _M = getModelInstance(p);
    _C = getControllerInstance(p);
    _M.setPlotWrapperController(_C);
    _C.setPlotWrapperModel(_M);
    _M.setPlot(p._plot);
}

```

```

/**
 * Method for creating the controller
   instance.
 *
 * @param p params container
 * @return plot wrapper controller
 */
protected PlotWrapperController
    getInstance(Params p)
{
    return new PlotWrapperController(this);
}

/**
 * Method for creating the model instance.
 *
 * @param p params container
 * @return plot wrapper model
 */
protected PlotWrapperModel getModelInstance
    (Params p)
{
    return new PlotWrapperModel(this);
}

/**
 * Can be overwritten to instantiate some
   additional GUI elements.
 *
 * @param p params container
 */
protected void instantiateGUI(Params p)
{
}

/**
 * Instantiates the layout.
 *
 * @param p params container
 */
protected void instantiateLayout(Params p)
{
    setLayout(new BorderLayout());
    add(_M._plot, BorderLayout.CENTER);
}

```

Let's now customize the plot wrapper. This tutorial calls the created extension "PlotAndButton". For this reason, *plotwrapper.AbstractPlotWrapper* and *plotwrapper.PlotWrapperModel* classes are extended. The implemented classes are named *PlotAndButton* and *PlotAndButtonModel*, and are stored in the "shared.plotwrapper" package (as they are also used in the following tutorial).

Regarding the model, the extending class is responsible for creating the button with a label specified by the user (and keeping the reference). The source code is provided in Listing 38 for convenience. Note that custom methods for creating and retrieving the button have been added.

Listing 38: PlotAndButtonModel class

```

package t1_10.t1_visualization_module.
    t7_top_level_components.shared.
    plotwrapper;

import plotwrapper.AbstractPlotWrapper;
import plotwrapper.PlotWrapperModel;

import javax.swing.*;

/**
 * Model for the {@link PlotAndButton}
   class.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class PlotAndButtonModel extends
    PlotWrapperModel
{
    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param plotWrapper reference to plot
       wrapper.
     */
    public PlotAndButtonModel(
        AbstractPlotWrapper plotWrapper)
    {
        super(plotWrapper);
    }

    /**
     * Reference to the button.
     */
    private JButton _button;

    /**
     * Auxiliary method for instantiating the
       button.
     *
     * @param label button label.
     */
    protected void createButton(String label)
    {
        _button = new JButton(label);
    }

    /**
     * Button getter.
     *
     * @return button getter.
     */
    protected JButton getButton()
    {
        return _button;
    }
}

```

When it comes to *PlotAndButton*, it introduces a few essential modifications to its parent class (see Listing 39 brought for convenience):

- The params container can now supply a label for the button.
- It constructs the *PlotAndButtonModel* model (instead of the basic *PlotWrapperModel*; see the *getModelInstance(Params p)* method).
- It requests the model to instantiate the button during GUI initialization.
- It adds the plot and the button to the panel and establishes the layout (during layout initialization).

Listing 39: PlotAndButton class

```

package t1_10.t1_visualization_module.
    t7_top_level_components.shared.
    plotwrapper;

import plot.AbstractPlot;
import plotwrapper.AbstractPlotWrapper;
import plotwrapper.PlotWrapperModel;

import java.awt.*;

/**
 * Extension of {@link AbstractPlotWrapper}
 * that contains a panel and a button.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class PlotAndButton extends
    AbstractPlotWrapper
{
    /**
     * Params container.
     */
    public static class Params extends
        AbstractPlotWrapper.Params
    {
        /**
         * Button label.
         */
        public final String _buttonLabel;

        /**
         * Parameterized constructor.
         *
         * @param plot      plot to be
         *                  displayed
         * @param buttonLabel button label
         */
        public Params(AbstractPlot plot, String
            buttonLabel)
        {
            super(plot);
            _buttonLabel = buttonLabel;
        }
    }

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param plot      plot to be
     *                  displayed
     * @param buttonLabel button label
     */
    public PlotAndButton(AbstractPlot plot,
        String buttonLabel)
    {
        this(new Params(plot, buttonLabel));
    }

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param p params container
     */
    public PlotAndButton(Params p)
    {
        super(p);
    }

    /**
     * Method for creating the model instance
     * (creates a custom model).
     *
     * @param p params container
     * @return plot wrapper model
     */
    @Override
    protected PlotWrapperModel
        getModelInstance(AbstractPlotWrapper.
            Params p)
    {
        return new PlotAndButtonModel(this);
    }

    /**
     * This custom "instantiateGUI" method
     * initialized the button.
     *
     * @param p params container
     */
    @Override
    protected void instantiateGUI(
        AbstractPlotWrapper.Params p)
    {
        setBackground(Color.WHITE);
        Params pp = (Params) p;
        ((PlotAndButtonModel) _M).createButton(
            pp._buttonLabel);
    }

    /**
     * Instantiates the layout. The wrapped
     * plot is assumed to occupy most of the
     * upper space, while the button is
     * assigned to the lower part of JPanel.
     *
     * @param p params container
     */
}

```

```

@Override
protected void instantiateLayout(
    AbstractPlotWrapper.Params p)
{
    GridBagLayout GBL = new GridBagLayout()
    ;
    setLayout(GBL);

    GridBagConstraints gbc = new
        GridBagConstraints();
    gbc.anchor = GridBagConstraints.
        PAGE_START;
    95
    gbc.fill = GridBagConstraints.BOTH;
    gbc.gridx = 0;
    gbc.gridy = 0;
    gbc.gridwidth = 1;
    gbc.gridheight = 1;
    100
    gbc.weightx = 99.0d;
    gbc.weighty = 99.0d;
    GBL.setConstraints(_M.getPlot(), gbc);
    add(_M.getPlot());

    105
    gbc.anchor = GridBagConstraints.
        PAGE_END;
    gbc.fill = GridBagConstraints.BOTH;
    gbc.gridx = 0;
    gbc.gridy = 1;
    gbc.gridwidth = 1;
    gbc.gridheight = 1;
    110
    gbc.weightx = 1.0d;
    gbc.weighty = 1.0d;

    GBL.setConstraints(((PlotAndButtonModel
        ) _M).getButton(), gbc);
    115
    add(((PlotAndButtonModel) _M).getButton
        ());
    120
}
}

```

Finally, **Tutorial1** shows how to instantiate the designed classes and display them. The most relevant code snippet from this source code is in Listing 40.

Listing 40: Creating and displaying a customized plot

```

// Plot customization:
// First, a custom plot wrapper object is
// instantiated (this custom implementation
// wraps the input plot and
// adds a button with the specified label).
PlotAndButton plotAndButton = new
    PlotAndButton(plot, "Button label");
    5

// Next, a default plots wrapper (
// aggregates plot wrappers) is
// instantiated (wraps the PlotAndButton
// wrapped
// created above).
PlotsWrapper plotsWrapper = new
    PlotsWrapper(plotAndButton);

    10
// Finally, a frame object is constructed.

```

```

Frame frame = new Frame(plotsWrapper, 0.5f)
;

```

9.2. Creating a custom plots wrapper [T]

Source package:

t1_t10.t1_visualization_module.t7_top_level_components.t2
and **shared**

This tutorial is a continuation of the one introduced in Section 9.1. It targets the plots wrapper component and shows how to extend it to achieve a result presented in Figure 58. Note that, however, the process is analogous to this given in Section 9.1. Therefore, the source codes are not brought here for brevity. Nonetheless, this tutorial also highlights that the plot wrapper controls the top-level plot-related logic, which can be parameterized via the params container (*plotswrapper.AbstractPlotsWrapper.Params*). Getting acquainted with its various fields and their JavaDoc comments is recommended. For example, consider the code snippet from **Tutorial2** presented in Listing 41. It shows how to supply the plots wrapper constructor with the params container. The given code reveals three parameterization fields:

- **_noUpdaterQueues**: As explained in Section 2.2, plots wrapper maintains a queueing system. The number of queues it maintains can be specified via this number. Note that one plot is explicitly maintained by one queue (but a queue can be assigned many plots). Hence, there is no reason to set the number of queues to be greater than the number of maintained plots. Also, there is an implicit upper limit of 8 above, which one cannot expect performance improvement. The default Java Swing thread pool size for swing workers (executed via these queues) dictates the upper limit. This limit equals 10, but two technical workers are continuously processing in the background. Hence, the overall limit can be considered 8. In this tutorial, setting this parameter to 2 is recommended, as there are two plots. If so, each plot will be assigned a dedicated queue. Therefore, a complete parallelization can be expected (of course, the parallelization efficiency is also hardware- and OS-dependent).
- **_animatorFPS**: The animator object is one of the two abovementioned swing workers being continuously processed. It is responsible for depicting the active render (*BufferedImage*) on the drawing area (basically, it just copies and pastes an image; it is a relatively fast operation). This parameter can adjust the frequency of triggering this procedure.
- **_interactorFPS**: Another continuously processed worker is responsible for handling interaction requests. First, various swing components (e.g., plots) are instantiated with keyboard/mouse-related listeners. When a keyboard or mouse event occurs, the processing is delegated to the

Figure 58: A window with customized plots and plot wrappers

interactor (timer; if used), which, at the specified frequency, delegates the processing further to an interact listener (see *listeners.interact* package). In the initial release of JECDM, only the *InteractListener3D* class implemented concrete functionality – allows manipulation of the projection in 3D mode. Changing the projection implies constructing a new render, which may be time-consuming. This field provides control of the frequency at which the interactor delegates processing to a specific implementation of an interact listener.

Listing 41: Creating and displaying a customized plot

```
// Next, a custom plot wrapped is
// instantiated. It accordingly places the
// left and right plots (wrappers) and
// adds additional button below them.
PlotsAndButton plotsAndButton = new
    PlotsAndButton(plotAndButtonLeft,
        plotAndButtonRight, "Main button");

// The plots wrapper can also be
// instantiated explicitly via the params
// container, which
// provides means for further customization
:
//PlotsAndButton.Params pPAB = new
    PlotsAndButton.Params(plotAndButtonLeft,
        plotAndButtonRight, "Main button");
//pPAB._noUpdatersQueues = 2;
//pPAB._animatorFPS = 60;
```

```
//pPAB._interactorFPS = 60;
//PlotsAndButton plotsAndButton = new
    PlotsAndButton(pPAB);
```

10. On the data updater

The tutorials we have covered showcased one way a plot can be supplied with data sets: calling the *plot.getModel().setDataSet(s)(...)* method. This approach is perfectly fine. However, it may be inconvenient if multiple plots and data sets are considered, non-standard display ranges parameterization is used, or the data is continuously being supplied from an external source, i.e., an optimizer. For this reason, a simple *updater.DataUpdater* class was implemented. It supports data upload automatization and allows the establishment of an efficient data flow from external sources to plots.

The data updater implements 3-layer processing whose general scheme is depicted in Figure 59. As for the first layer, the data updater involves at least one data source, which is an implementation of *updater.IDataSource* interface (see Listing 42). Data sources are responsible for providing raw, unprocessed data in the form of a *double[][]* matrix (see the *createData()* method in Listing 42) for further processing. For example, an implementation of *IDataSource* interface may be a simple wrapper for the optimizer, such as an evolutionary method. Calling for data creation could then construct and return a solution matrix (rows = solutions; columns = evaluations).

Figure 59: A general scheme of the data update process

Listing 42: IDataSource interface

```

/**
 * Interface for various implementations
 * providing new data to be processed by {
 * @link IDataProcessor}.
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public interface IDataSource
{
    /**
     * Should create a new data and returns
     * it.
     *
     * @return new data
     */
    double [][] createData();

    [...]
}

```

As showcased in Figure 59, the outputs from data sources are passed to data processors (implementations of *updater.IDataProcessor* interface; see Listing 43 and the *update(double[][] data)* method). The processors can perform some auxiliary data processing, e.g., collecting past data and returning all data that have been stored so far. Note that the default implementation, i.e., *updater.DataProcessor* does not perform extra processing but takes the input *double[][]* matrix and considers it an output as it is. Most importantly, each data source can be a data provider to multiple data processors. However, one data processor can only be assigned one data source to allow the implementation of some source-dedicated processing. **Important note:** the inputs are considered read-only. Hence, explicit manipulation of the input matrix is prohibited. Note that the output of the data processor should be in the *LinkedList<double[][]>* form (see Listing 43 and the *getData()* method). It is a format that is compatible with plot methods for data upload. Note that the method's description suggests creating a new *LinkedList* object (wrapper for *double[][]*-elements) each time the method is called to avoid potential concurrent modifications.

Listing 43: IDataProcessor interface

```

/**
 * Interface for classes responsible for
 * processing data to be provided to plots
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public interface IDataProcessor
{
    /**
     * The implementation be called to update
     * the internal data maintained by the
     * updater.
     *
     * @param sourceData new data to be
     * processed
     */
    void update(double [][] sourceData);

    /**
     * Getter for the data maintained (and
     * processed) by the updater.
     * When called, the method should
     * construct a new list that wraps the
     * maintained data and return it (to
     * avoid concurrent modifications).
     *
     * @return data
     */
    LinkedList<double [][]> getData();

    [...]
}

```

The third processing layer is related to providing data to plots. Each data processor must be assigned at least one plot. At the same time, one plot can have any number (non-negative) of designated data processors (if zero, its data will not be updated). The multiplicity of potential assignments is related to the fact that a plot may handle multiple data sets. Hence, a single data processor can be considered a data provider for a single data set maintained by the plot.

The introduced system is flexible and can be adjusted to serve various needs. However, having a basic understanding of the imposed data flow is essential to implementing an efficient processing system. Consider the following scenario, for instance. There is one data source that generates 3D points, which can be characterized by three attributes: *X*, *Y*, and *Z*. Let's assume that we want to display these points using three 2D plots that take the following perspectives: *[X, Y]*, *[X, Z]*, and *[Y, Z]*. It can be achieved in two ways:

1. Use one data source (which provides 3D points), three data processors (assigned with the source), each creating 2-element points from the input 3-element ones using a different combination of dimensions, and finally, three 2D plots that use a commonly parameterized display range manager.
2. Use one data source (which provides 3D points), one data processor that passes the input data as it is, and three 2D plots that have accordingly adjusted attribute-to-display-

range mapping.

The first approach seems more elegant and capable of future extensions (e.g., adding new, dimension-related attributes). However, the second approach is more efficient as no intermediate data is created, i.e., the data provided by the source is explicitly passed to plots with adjusted mappings.

Parameterizing the data updater. The data processing discussed above is handled by the `updater.DataUpdater` class that requires parameterization. As with most of the higher-level components that require parameterization, this class has an inner `Params` class that is considered a params container. It is brought in Listing 44 for convenience. Let's discuss its essential fields.

The first field, i.e., “`_dataSources`” is self-explanatory. All data sources that are to be used by the system should be provided via this array. Similarly, “`_dataProcessors`” array should store the data processors employed.

Listing 44: `updater.DataUpdater.Params` class

```
/**
 * Params container.
 */
public static class Params
{
    /**
     * Data sources.
     */
    public IDataSource[] _dataSources;

    /**
     * Data processors.
     */
    public IDataProcessor[] _dataProcessors;

    /**
     * Data sources -> data processor mappings
     (elements map 1:1 with the elements
     in _dataSources).
     */
    public SourceToProcessors[]
        _sourcesToProcessors;

    /**
     * Data processors -> plots mappings (
     elements map 1:1 with the elements in
     _dataProcessors).
     */
    public ProcessorsToPlots[]
        _processorsToPlots;

    /**
     * Reference to the plots wrapper.
     */
    protected final AbstractPlotsWrapper
        _plotsWrapper;

    /**
     * Auxiliary (can be null) map that binds
     a boolean flag with a plot.

```

```

 * The flag determines whether to request
   an update in display ranges when
   calling for
 * {@link plot.PlotModel#setDataSets(
   ArrayList, boolean)}. The default
   interpretation (e.g., when the flag
   is not
 * provided, is true). Nonetheless, the
   negative flags set in {@link
   drmanager.DisplayRangesManager.
   DisplayRange}
 * may negate the request.
 */
public HashMap<AbstractPlot, Boolean>
    _callForUpdateDisplayRanges = null;

[...]
}
```

The third field, i.e., “`_sourcesToProcessors`”, determines the sources-processors bindings. Important note: elements in this array are assumed to be implicitly associated with the elements of “`_dataSources`” (1:1 implicit mapping by element index). I.e., the bindings for the *i*-th processor are stored in the *i*-th element “`_sourcesToProcessors`”. The `SourceToProcessors` class wraps an indices pointing to different data processors stored in “`_dataProcessors`” (see Listing 45). Again, this is a 1:1 mapping by index.

Listing 45: `updater.SourceToProcessors` class

```
/**
 * Represents association: data source ->
   data processors.
 * This mapping implies that one data
   source can be used by multiple
   processors.
 */
public class SourceToProcessors
{
    /**
     * IDs (in-array indices) of associated
     data processors.
     */
    protected final int[] _processorID;

    [...]
}
```

Listing 46: `updater.ProcessorToPlots` class

```
/**
 * Represents association: data processors
   -> data plots
 * This mapping implies that multiple plots
   can use results of one processor.
 */
public class ProcessorToPlots
{
    /**
     * Reference data set objects used when
     constructing new ones.

```

```

10  * They provide info on the displayed
    * data sets styles and the painter used
    .
    * Each reference set is linked to one
    * plot id in the ''_plotIDs'' array.
    */
    protected final IDataset []
        _referenceDataSet;

15  /**
    * Plot ids linked with the data
    * processor.
    */
    protected final int[] _plotIDs;

20  [...]
    }

```

The following field (“*processorsToPlots*”) works analogously to the “*sourcesToProcessors*” array, but it binds processors with plots, obviously. The *Updater.ProcessorToPlots* class is brought in Listing 46 for convenience. The “*plotIDs*” is an indices array that points to various plots handled by the plots wrapper. Again, this is 1:1 mapping by index (i.e., the index of *i* stored in “*plotIDs*” as associated with the *i*-th plot handled by the plots wrapper; the order in which the plots are stored is determined by the user when instantiating the wrapper).

Note that the *ProcessorToPlots* class contains another array: “*referenceDataSet*”. Its elements are assumed to be connected 1:1 with elements stored in “*plotIDs*”. As discussed, a single data processor can be considered a data set provider. However, a data set style (marker/line) must also be supplied along with raw data for the plot to define how the data set will be rendered. This style can be supplied precisely via the “*referenceDataSet*” array. The “reference” means that the data set object is supposed to contain just the marker/line style definitions but no data (suitable static methods that allow constructing empty data sets are available in *dataset.DataSet* class). When providing data (*LinkedList<double[][]>*) to a plot, the data will be wrapped by a suitably parameterized data set object derived from the reference set (see the *IDataset.wrapAround(LinkedList<double[][]> data)* method that construct new data set object from another one by cloning marker/line styles stored in the reference data set). Notably, the same data set may be rendered differently on different plots by specifying different styles in the “*referenceDataSet*” array.

Next, the plots wrapper must be passed via the constructor when instantiating the params container. The data updater will access the plots from the wrapper when updating data sets.

Finally, the field “*callForUpdateDisplayRanges*” can be customized to specify which plots will be requested to update their display ranges during data upload. The default policy is that the display ranges are requested to be updated. Nonetheless, if some plots have fixed display ranges, there is no reason to call for such an update when updating their data. One may link a “false” value with a plot in this associative array to prevent this request.

10.1. Creating data updating system – an example [T]

Source package:
t1.t10.t1.visualization.module.t8.data.updater.t1 and
shared

This tutorial presents an example of the practical use of a data updater coupled with different plots. Consider the following scenario:

- Two external data sources provide a series of three-dimensional data points drawn from the Gaussian distribution. The means and standard deviations for the *X*, *Y*, and *Z* dimensions are treated as parameters and differ between the two data sources.
- The provided data points are expected to be depicted using two plots: the regular 3D plot and the parallel coordinate plot 2D. Each plot is supposed to illustrate two data sets: one per each source.
- The data points will be colored using a gradient, with each point’s color chosen based on its distance from the data set’s expected mean vector. Each data set will use a different gradient to distinguish between them.
- It is assumed that a data processor will supply the information about the distance. Hence, the data processor should implement the following transformation: $[X, Y, Z] \rightarrow [X, Y, Z, ((X - mean_X)^2 + (Y - mean_Y)^2 + (Z - mean_Z)^2)^{0.5}]$.
- It is presumed that data sources can provide the data online (i.e., in a series of data batches), and it will be the responsibility of data processors to keep the past data (the plots are to depict all data points stored so far).

The final render produced in this tutorial is illustrated in Figure 60 for clarity. Additionally, the conceptual scheme of the data updating process implemented in the source codes is given in Figure 61.

Listings 47 and 48 bring the implementations of *IDataSource* and *IDataProcessor* used in this tutorial. They are very straightforward; hence, there is no need to elaborate on them. Note that both implementations extend respective abstract classes that already implement some standard functionalities. It is worth highlighting that the *AbstractDataProcessor* provides mechanisms for collecting past data in a *LinkedList* and introduces a new method “*protected double[][] getProcessedData(double[][] sourceData)*” that can be overwritten (instead of the main method imposed by the interface: *LinkedList<double[][]> getData()*) to process only the current data (shortcut; *LinkedList<double[][]> getData()* is implemented in the abstract class and handles the past data, it delegates the processing to the *getProcessedData* method).

Finally, listing 49 brings the most relevant code snippet from this tutorial’s source code, which is focused on creating a suitably parameterized data updater object. It explains step-by-step how to create data sources and processors and how to bind involved components to establish a desired processing flow.

Figure 60: Combining a data updater with multiple plots – expected render

Figure 61: Conceptual scheme of data updating process

Listing 47: Implemented data source

```

public class GaussianGenerator extends
    AbstractSource implements IDataSource
{
    /**
     * The number of points to generate when
     * requested.
     */
    private final int _n;

    /**
     * Space dimensionality.
     */
    private final int _m;
  
```

```

/**
 * Means (i-th element is linked to i-th
 * dimension).
 */
private final double[] _means;

/**
 * Standard deviations (i-th element is
 * linked to i-th dimension).
 */
private final double[] _stds;

/**
 * Random number generator.
 */
  
```

```

private final IRandom _R;

/**
 * Parameterized constructor.
 *
 * @param n the number of points to
 *         generate when requested
 * @param m space dimensionality
 * @param means means (i-th element is
 *         linked to i-th dimension)
 * @param stds standard deviations (i-th
 *         element is linked to i-th dimension)
 * @param R random number generator
 */
public GaussianGenerator(int n, int m,
    double[] means, double[] stds, IRandom
    R)
{
    _n = n;
    _m = m;
    _means = means;
    _stds = stds;
    _R = R;
}

/**
 * Creates new data and returns it (
 * random points drawn from the Gaussian
 * distribution).
 *
 * @return new data
 */
@Override
public double[][] createData()
{
    double[][] p = new double[_n][_m];
    for (int i = 0; i < _n; i++)
        for (int j = 0; j < _m; j++)
            p[i][j] = _means[j] + _R.
                nextGaussian() * _stds[j];
    return p;
}
}

```

Listing 48: Implemented data processor

```

public class DistanceProcessor extends
    AbstractDataProcessor implements
    IDataProcessor
{
    /**
     * Space dimensionality.
     */
    private final int _m;

    /**
     * Means (i-th element is linked to i-th
     * dimension).
     */
    private final double[] _means;

    /**

```

```

 * Parameterized constructor.
 *
 * @param m space dimensionality
 * @param means means (i-th element is
 *         linked to i-th dimension)
 */
public DistanceProcessor(int m, double[]
    means)
{
    super(new Params(true)); // true = use
        the cumulative mode
    _m = m;
    _means = means;
}

/**
 * Appends to input data points their
 * distances to expected mean.
 *
 * @param sourceData source data
 * @return processed data
 */
@Override
protected double[][] getProcessedData(
    double[][] sourceData)
{
    double[][] processed = new double[
        sourceData.length][_m + 1];
    double d;
    for (int i = 0; i < sourceData.length;
        i++)
    {
        double sum = 0.0d;
        for (int j = 0; j < _m; j++)
        {
            processed[i][j] = sourceData[i][j];
            d = sourceData[i][j] - _means[j];
            sum += d * d;
        }
        processed[i][_m] = Math.sqrt(sum);
    }
    return processed;
}
}

```

Listing 49: Creating and parameterizing the data updater

```

// It's time now to construct the data
// updater. First, we need to create a
// params container. Note that the plots
// wrapper must be passed via the
// constructor. The data updater will
// access the plots from the wrapper when
// updating data sets.
DataUpdater.Params pP = new DataUpdater.
    Params(wrapper);

// The lines below create two data sources
// that provide points drawn randomly from
// a parameterized Gaussian
// distribution (see the GaussianGenerator
// class in the shared package).

```

```

pP._dataSources = new IDataSource[2];
pP._dataSources[0] = new GaussianGenerator
    (100, 3, means0, new double[]{0.3d, 0.2d
    , 0.3d}, R);
10 pP._dataSources[1] = new GaussianGenerator
    (100, 3, means1, new double[]{0.1d, 0.5d
    , 0.1d}, R);

// Next, we must create two data processors
// , each linked to a different data source
// . Even though these processors
// perform the same operations, they must
// be unique to each source. The reason is
// that the processor may still
// perform some source-dependent operations
// , as in this example. The
// DistanceProcessor class extends the
15 // AbstractDataProcessor, which implements
// mechanisms that allow past data to be
// stored and returned along
// with the current data via the LinkedList
// <double[][]> (each element is related to
// one data update called on
// the processor object). This ‘‘cumulative
// ’’ mode is explicitly enabled in the
// DistanceProcessor.
pP._dataProcessors = new IDataProcessor[2];
pP._dataProcessors[0] = new
    DistanceProcessor(3, means0);
20 pP._dataProcessors[1] = new
    DistanceProcessor(3, means1);

// The lines below establish sources-
// processor bindings (note that, in
// general, each source may be connected
// with multiple processors, but one
// processor may be linked with only one
// source).
pP._sourcesToProcessors = new
    SourceToProcessors[2];
25 pP._sourcesToProcessors[0] = new
    SourceToProcessors(0);
pP._sourcesToProcessors[1] = new
    SourceToProcessors(1);

// The lines below establish sources-
// processor bindings (note that, in
// general, each source may be connected
// with multiple processors, but one
// processor may be linked with only one
// source). The code below links
30 // source #0 with processor #0 and source
// #1 with processor #1.
pP._processorToPlots = new ProcessorToPlots
    [2];
int[] plotIds = new int[]{0, 1};

// The following two blocks of code
// establish processor-plots bindings. In
// this tutorial, each processor
35 // provides the output to two plots (Plot3D
// and ParallelCoordinatePlot2D).

```

```

{
// Creating reference data sets (each for
// each targeted plot):
IDataSet RDS0 = DataSet.getFor3D("DS0",
    new MarkerStyle(0.02f, Gradient.
    getViridisGradient(), 3, Marker.
    SPHERE_LOW_POLY_3D));
IDataSet RDS1 = DataSet.
    getForParallelCoordinatePlot2D("DS0",
    3, new LineStyle(0.1f, Gradient.
    getViridisGradient(), 3));
40 IDataset[] referenceDataSets = new
    IDataset[]{RDS0, RDS1};
// Creating the binding (processor #0 ->
// two plots):
pP._processorToPlots[0] = new
    ProcessorToPlots(plotIds,
    referenceDataSets);
}
{
// Creating reference data sets (each for
// each targeted plot):
IDataSet RDS0 = DataSet.getFor3D("DS1",
    new MarkerStyle(0.02f, Gradient.
    getPlasmaGradient(), 3, Marker.
    SPHERE_LOW_POLY_3D));
IDataSet RDS1 = DataSet.
    getForParallelCoordinatePlot2D("DS1",
    3, new LineStyle(0.1f, Gradient.
    getPlasmaGradient(), 3));
45 IDataset[] referenceDataSets = new
    IDataset[]{RDS0, RDS1};
// Creating the binding (processor #1 ->
// two plots):
pP._processorToPlots[1] = new
    ProcessorToPlots(plotIds,
    referenceDataSets);
}
}

```

References

- [1] M. Tomczyk and M. Kadziński, “Interactive tool for visualizing the comprehensive performance of evolutionary multi-objective algorithms applied to problems with two or three objectives,” in *Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference Companion, GECCO ’24 Companion*, pp. 375–378, Association for Computing Machinery, 2024.